

PIACERE

Deliverable D8.3

Dissemination, Communication and Networking Report

Editor(s):	Leire Orue-Echevarria, Maitena Ilardia, Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI)
Responsible Partner:	TECNALIA
Status-Version:	Final – v1.0
Date:	31.05.2022
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	101000162
Project Title:	PIACERE

Title of Deliverable:	Dissemination, Communication and Networking Report
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	31.05.2022

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP8
Editor(s):	Maitena Ilardia (TECNALIA)
Contributor(s):	Maitena Ilardia (TECNALIA), Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI), Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA)
Reviewer(s):	Juncal Alonso (TECNALIA)
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	All WPs

Abstract:	<p>This deliverable will explain the dissemination and communication activities followed during the reporting periods as well as the results from these activities and will update project's dissemination and communication plan respectively.</p> <p>This report will also contain the relevant activities executed to foster a close collaboration with projects related to PIACERE, as well as future networking plans.</p>
Keyword List:	Communication, KPIs,
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Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	09.02.2022	First draft version	Maitena Ilardia (TECNALIA)
v0.2	22.02.2022	Comments and suggestions received by consortium partners	ALL
V0.3	11.03.2022	Dissemination results and activities	Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI)
V0.4	13.05.2022	Ready for internal review	Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI), Maitena Ilardia (TECNALIA)
V1.0	31.05.2022	Final version for submission	Juncal Alonso (Tecnalia)

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Terms and abbreviations

CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D8.3) is a public report, result of the activities on communication and dissemination of Work Package 8 -Sustainability and Awareness- and is the first one of two deliverables explaining the dissemination and communication activities followed during the reporting periods, as well as the results from these activities. This report also contains the relevant activities executed to foster a close collaboration with EU projects related to PIACERE, as well as some future networking plans.

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1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

PIACERE partners fully understand the importance of increasing the knowledge about the project and its outcomes and are fully committed to contributing to various dissemination, communication, and networking activities. Here, we list and describe the results achieved during the first eighteen months of the project based on the communication and dissemination strategy outlined in D8.2 [1], [2],[3].

1.2 Document structure

Section 1 gives a general introduction, scope, and structure of this deliverable. Section 2 summarises the main results in terms of dissemination, communication, and networking activities. Section 3 describes in detail the dissemination material that was created during the 18-month reporting period. Section 4 focuses on the PIACERE communication strategy and monitoring KPIs, as well as it describes the tools that were used during the reporting period (project website, blog and social networks). Section 5 presents the dissemination activities and results in terms of scientific publications of the PIACERE partners, as well as workshops, seminars, and business dissemination events in which the consortium has participated to promote the project. Also, this section presents the monitoring procedure and dissemination KPIs. Section 6 gives an overview of the PIACERE network activities with other EU projects. Finally, in Section 7 we draw conclusion.

2 Overall PIACERE dissemination and communication results

2.1 Dissemination Results

This section presents briefly the dissemination results obtained by the PIACERE consortium [1] in terms of scientific activities in the period M1-M18. More details with regard to the monitoring and assessment based on relevant KPIs are given in section 5.6.2 of this deliverable D8.3 Dissemination, communication and networking report - Report - v1.

The dissemination strategy outlined in the previous deliverable D8.2 [1] has led to the following scientific dissemination results in terms of published scientific journal and conference papers in the first reporting period M1-M18 (for more details see Table 9 in section 5.6):

International journals

J1. Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Maider Huarte. ACSml: A solution to address the challenges of Cloud services federation and monitoring towards the Cloud Continuum. Special issue on "Smart Cloud Applications, Services and Technologies", *International Journal of Computational Science and Engineering*. Inderscience. 2021. [H-21, Q3]

This paper presents a solution for Cloud Brokerage and monitoring. ACSml serves as baseline for the implementation of the IEC (Infrastructural Elements Catalogue) and the performance monitoring Key results in PIACERE.

J2. Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Eneko Osaba, Iñigo Martinez, Josu Diaz de Arcaya. Optimization and Prediction Techniques for Self-Healing and Self-Learning Applications in a Trustworthy Cloud Continuum. *MDPI - Information Journal*. Special Issue "Artificial Intelligence for the Cloud Continuum". Information 2021, 12, 308. Publisher MDPI. Basel. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info12080308> [Q2]

This paper presents the approach that will be followed in PIACERE for the IOP and the SelfLearning.

J3. Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto. Resource calendaring for mobile edge computing: Centralized and decentralized optimization approaches. *Computer Networks* (ELSEVIER), 2021. open access, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comnet.2021.108426> [H-135, Q1]

Resource calendaring permits to exploit the intrinsic flexibility in the services demanded by different users, whose starting time can be shifted without penalizing the utility perceived by the user while, at the same time, permitting a better resource utilization in the network. Both the centralized and decentralized optimization approaches for resource calendaring studied in this paper can be used in PIACERE IOP in the edge computing scenarios.

J4. Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto. Joint planning of network slicing and mobile edge computing: Models and algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing*. Open access. Available online:

<https://www.computer.org/csdl/journal/cc/5555/01/09521805/1wkrmdXmjdk> [H-49, Q1]

Jointly planning the availability of computational resources at the edge, the slicing of mobile network and edge computation resources allows the network operator to fine tune the network operation cost and the total latency experienced by users. The optimization approach for resource planning studied in this paper can be used in PIACERE IOP in the edge computing scenarios.

J5. Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto. A dataset for mobile edge computing network topologies, *Data in Brief*, Volume 39, 2021, 107557, ISSN 2352-3409, open access, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2021.107557>. [**H-27, Q4**]

In the present paper we provide data related to 3 randomly generated topologies, with increasing network size (from 25 to 100 nodes). Moreover, we propose a MEC topology generated from OpenCellID real data and concerning the Base Stations' location of 234 LTE cells owned by a mobile operator (Vodafone) in the center of Milan. We also provide realistic reference parameters (link bandwidth computation and storage capacity, offered traffic), derived from real services provided by MEC in the deployment of 5G networks.

J6. Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Maider Huarte. CloudOps: Towards the Operationalization of the Cloud Continuum. *MDPI Applied Sciences*. Basel 2022, 12(9), Available online:

<https://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/forthcoming.php?jcode=ijcse> [**Q2**]

This paper presents a solution for Cloud Brokerage and monitoring. ACSml serves as baseline for the implementation of the IEC (Infrastructural Elements Catalogue) and the performance monitoring Key results in PIACERE.

International Conferences

C1. Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto. Resource calendaring for mobile edge computing in 5G networks. *IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*. IEEE, 2021. [**A***]

Resource calendaring permits to exploit the intrinsic flexibility in the services demanded by different users, whose starting time can be shifted without penalizing the utility perceived by the user while, at the same time, permitting a better resource utilization in the network. The optimization approach for resource calendaring studied in this paper can be used in PIACERE IOP in the edge computing scenarios.

C2. Juncal Alonso, Christophe Joubert, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Matteo Pradella, Daniel Vladusic. Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a Secure Framework. *First SWForum workshop on trustworthy software and open source (SWForum.eu)*. CEUR-WS.org, ISSN 1613-0073 Vol 2878. Open access. Online. 2021, pp. 16-23.

This paper presents PIACERE as a whole at conceptual level. The presentation in the workshop has been used to gather feedback on the PIACERE solution and approach.

C3. Galia Nedeltcheva, Alfonso De La Fuente Ruiz, Leire Orue-Echevarria Arrieta, Nejc Bat, Lorenzo Blasi. Towards Supporting the Generation of Infrastructure as Code Through Modelling Approaches – Systematic Literature Review. 2022 IEEE 19th International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C). *First International Workshop on the Foundations of Infrastructure Specification and Testing (FIST 2022)*. IEEE, Hawaii. 12-14 March 2022. eCF Paper Id: 1643378438288

The paper presents a structured literature review (SLR) for what concerns the aspects: Infrastructure as a Code (IaC) languages, modelling approaches supporting the generation of IaC, categories of languages, and their characteristics, and security analysis techniques. An extensive study has been performed on the generation of the Infrastructure as Code modelling approaches that are relevant to PIACERE DOML (DevSecOps modelling language) specifically, in order to study which DOML requirements could be satisfied by each approach.

C4. Michele Chiari, Michele De Pascalis, Matteo Pradella. Static Analysis of Infrastructure as Code: a Survey. 2022 IEEE 19th International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C). *First International Workshop on the Foundations of Infrastructure Specification and Testing (FIST 2022)*. IEEE, Hawaii. 12-14 March 2022.

This is a literature review on static analysis approaches for IaC, which covers methods based on code smell detection, data mining, and model checking. Its purpose within the project was to analyse the state of the art on static verification tools upon which to build the DOML Model Checker (WP4).

C5. Michele Chiari, Elisabetta Di Nitto, Adrián Noguero Mucientes, Bin Xiang. Developing a New DevOps Modelling Language to Support the Creation of Infrastructure as Code. *European Conference on Service-Oriented and Cloud Computing (ESOCC 2022)*. 22-24 March 2022. Online.

This is a short paper giving an overview of the motivations for building the DOML, the principles behind it, and its current structure. In this paper we have not introduced new developments, but its purpose is pure dissemination, to receive feedback on the DOML ideas from an expert external audience.

C6. Eneko Osaba, Josu Diaz de Arcaya, Leire Orue-Echavarria, Juncal Alonso, Jesus L. Lobo, Gorka Benguria, Iñaki Etxaniz. PIACERE Project: Description and Prototype for Optimizing Infrastructure as Code Deployment Configurations. The Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (**GECCO 2022**). Boston, USA, 9-13 July 2022. Hybrid mode. <https://gecco-2022.sigevo.org/>

The goal of this technical paper is to describe the preliminary approach followed in PIACERE for carrying out this optimization, and how the IOP fits into the whole PIACERE ecosystem. Additionally, results obtained in a preliminary experimentation are detailed in this study.

In short, the dissemination results in terms of scientific activities obtained by month M18 (for more details see Table 8 in section 5.6.2 and Table 9 in section 5.7) are as follows:

- Scientific activities:
 - o Journal papers: 6
 - o Conference papers: 6
 - o Cloud community, software and service publications: 10
 - o Attendance of events: 5
 - o Project newsletters: 1
 - o Project Posters: 1

2.2 Communication Results

In the first period of the project, there have been used different communication channels to facilitate the partners the execution of the project activities, particularly web page, blog and social networks. Several project materials have been provided, including press releases, brochure, poster, presentation slides and newsletters, so that the interested parties can complete the dissemination tasks (see Section 3). The different material gives an overview of the project, its objectives, results and expected impacts to keep informed about the activities executed in the PIACERE project.

One objective faced by PIACERE has been the publication of blog posts with the aim of discussing those topics related to the partners' knowledge that are being developed in the project activities. Additionally, in the 'Communication Materials' section, it is possible to find the press releases, newsletters, brochures and posters used for the communication work as well as it has been planned, all the deliverables to be available at the 'Public deliverables' section.

The different social media platforms have been used to reach more audience. Their use has increased the communication and interaction with the target communities, other research projects, and general public who are enthusiastic about, IaC and DevOps topics. The selected media channels have been mainly Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube and SlideShare.

PIACERE project has also used Google Analytics to monitor the behaviour of the website, that is, geographical information, audience, acquisition of the traffic channels of the different social networks, etc. This information is relevant to understand the operation and wellness of the different social networks and to evaluate the progress of the PIACERE website. The description of the PIACERE communication activities is reported in Section 4.

2.3 Networking Results

PIACERE partners understand the value of collaborating with other projects and initiatives beyond European projects.

The networking and collaboration with other European project are a natural process as synergies can be easily found. Some of the collaborations. PIACERE has participated in the following events organized by H-Cloud and HUB4CLOUD: H-cloud summit 2020, Digital Autonomy in the Computing Continuum Workshop, H-cloud summit 2021, Horizon Cloud summit 2022. PIACERE was invited to participate in the SODALITE Final event.

SWForum is another Coordination and Support Action (CSA), SWForum has organized three events in which representatives of PIACERE have been present; First SWForum workshop, Second SWForum workshop, SWForum Governance model workshop.

PIACERE appears in the project hub that SWForum has created and has participated in the MTRL assessment.

The Future Cloud Cluster was created by the European Commission with the aim of "providing a forum for discussion and collaboration for research and innovation initiatives that address next generation Cloud Computing challenges and issues, including diverse forms of distributed computing (Cloud, Multi-Cloud, Edge, Fog, Ad-hoc and Mobile computing. the work of the cluster has revolved around two main topics: Research roadmap, and Cloud Federation Reference Architecture.

Gaia-X is an initiative initially launched by Germany and France but now European that aims at creating a European federated data infrastructure. Some of the most relevant activities related to PIACERE include:

- Participation in the working group of Compliance.
- Participation in the working group Self-Description, where the attributes defined in the PIACERE IEC (Infrastructural Elements Catalogue).
- Development of the orchestrator, one of the Lots awarded in the German project GXFS.
- Online meeting with Pierre Gronlier, CTO of Gaia-X in spring 2021.

The Gaia-X Spanish Hub Working Group on Industry 4.0 was launched on February 15th, 2022 in Bilbao.

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3 Brand identity and project materials

This section presents the communication channels that have been used to establish the PIACERE brand identity and ensures that all project activities, such as reports, brochure, poster, presentation slides and newsletter have a competent and similar vision. PIACERE brand identity refers to the visual aspects in organizational communication and that all project partners will consider when developing the dissemination and communication materials.

3.1 Project logo

One of the most important things perceived to strengthen and thus increase the visibility and dissemination of a project is the brand identity. Thus, the logo is one of the main elements of identity and will be added to all graphic material and documents related to the project, where the logo and design represent the idea and vision of the PIACERE project.

The following logo has been designed for PIACERE's project:

Figure 1. PIACERE project Logo

3.2 Project presentation slides

The PIACERE project presentation slides have been designed to be used by all partners when presenting the project results at events, workshops and meetings. The project presentation slides will be continuously updated during the project period duration.

The presentation template includes an overview of the project, objectives, focus, goal, partners and contact information.

Figure 2. PIACERE presentation slides

3.3 Project brochure

The objective of the brochure is to convey knowledge of the objectives of PIACERE project, giving an overview of the key results, approach, benefits, use cases and project consortium. The brochure contains four pages, and it was designed to be viewed both in digital and printed formats with the aim to raise visibility of the project and can be distributed in the different workshops, conferences and events that the partners attend.

PIACERE's brochure contains four pages and provides information about the project key results, approach, benefits, use cases and a representation of the map for the different companies that accomplish the consortium.

Due to Covid pandemic we have not printed the brochure yet, but it is expected to be printed for the upcoming physical events. However, it is accessible at:

<https://www.piacere-project.eu/sites/d8piacere/files/documents/brochure%20Website%20Piacere.pdf>

PIACERE
Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a sEcuRE framework

KEY RESULTS

- KR1: CertificatioDevSecOps Modelling Language
- KR2: PIACERE Integrated Development Environment
- KR3: Infrastructural Code Generator
- KR4: DOML Extension mechanism
- KR5: Verification Tool
- KR6: IaC Code Security Inspector
- KR7 - Component Security Inspector
- KR8 – Canary Sandbox Environment (CSE)
- KR9 – IaC Optimized Platform (IOP)
- KR10 - IaC Execution Platform (IEP)
- KR11 – PIACERE Self-learning and self-healing mechanisms
- KR12 - Runtime security monitoring

APPROACH

BENEFITS

- Making the creation of such infrastructural code more accessible to the DevSecOps teams
- Increasing the quality, security, trustworthiness and evolvability of infrastructural code
- Ensuring business continuity by providing self-healing mechanisms anticipation of failures and violations
- Allowing IaC to self-learn from previous conditions that triggered un-expected situations

USE CASES

- SI-MPA. The Slovenian Ministry of Public Administration for hosting information systems on a centralized infrastructure
- PRODEVELOP. Critical Maritime Infrastructures for fulfil the management needs of port authorities
- ERICSSON. Public Safety on IoT in 5G of both human and IoT devices

CONSORTIUM

CONTACT INFORMATION
Project Coordinator:
Leire Orue-Echevarria
Leire.Orue-Echevarria@tecnalia.com
+34 664 103 005

Web: <http://piacere-project.eu>
Twitter: <https://twitter.com/PIACEREproject>
LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/in/PiacereH2020
Slideshare: www.slideshare.net/PIACERECOMMUNITY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952633

Figure 3. PIACERE brochure

3.4 Project poster

The main goal of the poster is to use in the different events, conferences, and workshops for the dissemination of the project results.

In the first 18 months of the project, a poster has been created around the topic ‘Enhancing the generation of Infrastructure as code through DevOps Modelling Language (DOML)’. This poster introduces the infrastructure-as-code (IaC) concept and definition. PIACERE will provide an integrated DevSecOps framework to develop, verify, release, configure, provision, and monitor infrastructure as code. Results will develop a solution covering the IaC lifecycle that will aid DevSecOps teams and will be validated into the PIACERE three use cases. Finally, it also includes PIACERE partners’ logos and contact.

This poster is available through the project website: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/sites/d8piacere/files/PIACERE%20Poster.pdf>

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Authors
Maitena Iardía, TECNALIA
Galia Novakova, POLIMI

Enhancing the generation of Infrastructure as Code through DevOps Modelling Language (DOML)

Introduction

Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) enables the automation of several deployments, configurations and management tasks that otherwise would have to be performed manually by an operator. IaC has a lot of potential in a cloud computing context as it results in a significant saving of time when an application needs to be redeployed on a different set of resources or needs to be extended with new components, even possibly running on different cloud infrastructures. In these cases, in fact, the infrastructural code can be reused, adapted, if needed, and then run for recreating very quickly the new or extended software instance.

PIACERE DevSecOps approach and framework

To achieve the IaC DevSecOps concept, PIACERE will provide an integrated DevSecOps framework to develop, verify, release, configure, provision, and monitor infrastructure as code. The extensible architecture and modular approach of PIACERE will support the different DevSecOps activities. Using a single integrated environment to develop (IDE) infrastructural code will unify the automation of the main DevSecOps activities and will shorten the learning curve for new DevSecOps teams. PIACERE will allow DevSecOps teams to model different infrastructure environments, by means of abstractions, through a novel DevOps Modelling Language (DOML), thus hiding the specificities and technicalities of the current solutions and increasing the productivity of these teams. Moreover, PIACERE will also provide an extensible infrastructural Code Generator (ICG), translating DOML into source files for different existing IaC tools, to reduce the time needed for creating infrastructural code for complex applications.

Results

PIACERE will develop a solution covering the IaC lifecycle that will aid DevSecOps teams in:

- 1) enhancing their IaC development, verification, optimization, configuration, orchestration and operation processes,
- 2) improving developers' and operators' productivity by shortening their learning curve,
- 3) while ensuring the IaC correctness and Quality of Service (QoS) against violations in its whole life, facilitating reconfigurations and predicting problems,
- 4) as well as decreasing the time-to-market.

Figure 1. First DOML example in PIACERE project illustrates how realistic applications and their supporting infrastructure can be specified

Conclusions

The novel concept of the PIACERE DevSecOps framework to develop and operate IaC can address current challenges and increase the quality, security, trustworthiness and evolvability of the infrastructural code. The first proof of concepts (PoC) of the solution have been released in the end of 2021. These initial versions of the components will be validated in the PIACERE pilots in three different business domains (i.e. Public Administrations, Critical Maritime Infrastructures and Public Safety on IoT in 5G) and will be then reviewed and enhanced in the following releases

Contact
Maitena Iardía
Communication
manager
Tel.: +34 954 103 325
maitena.iardia@tecnalia.com
www.tecnalia.com

Figure 4. PIACERE Poster

3.5 Press Releases

The press release in PIACERE, intends to promote the dissemination of the results of the project. Thus, the specialized communication media can discover about the work fulfilled in the project.

Next Figure 5 shows the English version of the press release.

Figure 5. PIACERE project Press Release

3.5.1 Press Release dissemination by the different partners

The press releases of the PIACERE partners has been disseminated through the PIACERE's partners social networks. It can be found an example of this work in the table:

Table 1. PIACERE's partners Press Release dissemination

XLAB	
<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/xlab_si/status/1526118204397035521</p>	
PRODEVELOP	
<p>LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/prodevelop_piacere-a-devsecops-framework-for-secure-activity-6931637611836936192-BY94?utm_source=linkedin_share&utm_medium=member_desktop_web</p>	
<p>Website: https://www.prodevelop.es/en/piacere-a-devsecops-framework-for-secure-iac-development-and-operation</p>	

PIACERE: A DevSecOps framework for secure IaC Development and Operation

Support to easily model the resources, network and infrastructural requirements

Automatic IaC orchestration

Monitor IaC and predict failures

Behaviour simulation of the IaC based on an optimized deployment configuration

DEV IaC OPS

CREATE PLAN RELEASE CONFIRM MONITOR VERIFY

PIACERE is an H2020 research project funded by the European Commission over a period of three years. PIACERE's main objective is Programming trustworthy Infrastructure As Code in a secure framework.

The PIACERE consortium, led by TECHNALIA, assembles a balanced set of academic and industrial partners, which play key roles in the EU DevSecOps ecosystem, ERICSSON, PRODEVELOP, POLIMI, HPE, XLAB, GCYS, BULLS.COM and TECHNALIA, are from four different countries, representing Northern and Southern Europe. TECHNALIA has been entrusted with the leadership of the consortium.

PIACERE aims to increase the productivity of DevOps teams in the development and operation of IaC through the provisioning of an integrated DevSecOps framework. DevOps teams can program IaC, as if they were programming any software application.

PIACERE will support the different DevSecOps activities through a single integrated environment to develop (IDE) infrastructural code that will unify the automation of the main DevSecOps activities and will shorten the learning curve for new DevSecOps teams. PIACERE will allow DevSecOps teams to model different infrastructure environments, by means of abstractions, through a novel DevOps Modelling Language (DOML), thus hiding the specificities and technicalities of the current solutions and increasing the productivity of these teams. Moreover, PIACERE will also provide an extensible Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG), translating DOML into source files for different existing IaC tools, to reduce the time needed for creating infrastructural code for complex applications. The provided extensibility mechanisms (DOML-E) shall ensure the sustainability and longevity of the PIACERE approach and tool-suite (new languages and protocols that can appear in the near future).

Another key innovation of PIACERE is a comprehensive toolkit for verification and trustworthiness. Firstly, a verification tool (V), that will apply static analysis to both the abstract model and the related infrastructural code, to execute consistency checks and other quality verifications according to identified best practices. Secondly, an IaC Code Security Inspector that will offer a form of Static Analysis Security Testing (SAST) by checking the IaC code against the known cybersecurity issues (misconfigurations, use of non-secure libraries, non-secure configuration patterns). Thirdly, a Component Security Inspector that by analysing also the IaC code, reports the potential vulnerabilities and proposes potential fixes. Fourth, a Canary environment that will allow unit testing of the behaviour of the infrastructural code on an isolated environment, which would enable the simulation of conditions for the production environment and identify some of the most common anti-patterns.

In the Ops part of the DevSecOps lifecycle, PIACERE also presents several key innovations: The Optimized Platform (OP) will present the DevSecOps teams with the most appropriate deployment configurations that best meet their defined constraints out of their catalogue of services, resources and infrastructural elements by means of optimization algorithms. The Execution Platform will automatically plan, prepare, and provision the infrastructure and plan, prepare, and install the corresponding software elements needed for the application to seamlessly run. At runtime, PIACERE will continuously monitor the metrics associated with the defined measurable KPIs (e.g. performance, availability, and security) through the runtime security monitoring and will be able to self-learn, implementing machine learning algorithms, and realizing an incremental learning strategy by continuously analysing divergences in the decision boundaries and detecting anomalies in the metrics being collected while retaining only the most up to date data to avoid model degradation. Whenever these self-learning mechanisms detect an anomaly or a potential SLA violation, an alarm will be triggered, and a self-healing mechanism launched. A self-healing mechanism will entail to launch optimisation algorithm for the actual problem domain and an automatic execution platform, monitoring and so on.

PIACERE approach and toolset will be assessed in three real use cases. SI-MPA will deploy an scenario for The Slovenian Ministry of Public Administration, Prodevelop will validate it in Critical Maritime Infrastructures Management, and Ericsson will verify the solution in a Public Safety on IoT in 5G use case.

PIACERE will also raise the following expected benefits:

- Making the creation of such infrastructural code more accessible to the DevSecOps teams
- Increasing the quality, security, trustworthiness and evolvability of infrastructural code

POLIMI

Website: <https://www.deib.polimi.it/eng/h2020-project/details/437>

PIACERE – A DevSecOps Framework for Secure IaC Development and Operation

Research Area: [Computer Science and Engineering](#)

Responsible: [DI NITTO ELISABETTA](#)

Research Lines: [Advanced software architectures and methodologies](#)

Web site: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

Horizon 2020 | DEIB Role: Partner | Start date: 2020-12-01 | Length: 36 months

Project abstract

PIACERE is a H2020 research project funded by the European Commission with the main objective of programming reliable infrastructures using Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC) in a secure framework.

PIACERE aims to increase the productivity of DevOps teams in the development and operation of IaC through the provisioning of an integrated DevSecOps framework that will allow them to program IaC as if they were programming any software application.

PIACERE will support the different DevSecOps activities through a single **integrated environment to develop (IDE)** infrastructural code that will unify the automation of the main DevSecOps activities and will shorten the learning curve for new DevSecOps teams. PIACERE will allow DevSecOps teams to model different infrastructure environments, by means of abstractions, through a new **DevOps Modeling Language (DOML)**. In addition, it will also provide an **extensible Infrastructure Code Generator (ICG)**, translating DOML into source files for several existing IaC tools.

Another key innovation of PIACERE is a **comprehensive toolkit for verification and trustworthiness**. Firstly, a **verification tool (VT)**, that will apply static analysis to both the abstract model and the related infrastructure code, to perform consistency checks and other quality verifications according to identified best practices. Secondly, an **IaC Code Security Inspector** that will offer a form of **Static Analysis Security Testing (SAST)** by checking the IaC code against known cybersecurity issues. Thirdly, a **Component Security Inspector** that, by analysing also the IaC code, reports potential vulnerabilities and proposes potential fixes. Fourthly, a **Canary environment** that will allow unit testing of the behavior of the infrastructural code by simulating the conditions of the production environment and identifying some of the most common anti-patterns.

In the Ops part of the DevSecOps lifecycle, PIACERE also features several key innovations: The **Optimized Platform (IOP)** will present the DevSecOps teams with the most appropriate deployment configurations that best meet their defined constraints out of their catalogue of services, resources and infrastructural elements by means of optimization algorithms. The **Execution Platform** will automatically plan, prepare and provision the infrastructure and plan, prepare and install the corresponding software elements needed for the application to seamlessly run. At runtime, PIACERE will continuously monitor the metrics associated with the defined measurable NFRs and will be able to **self-learn**, implementing **machine learning** algorithms and realizing an **incremental learning** strategy.

The PIACERE approach and toolset will be assessed in three **real use cases**: the deployment of a scenario for the Slovenian Ministry of Public Administration, the management of critical maritime infrastructures and a case of public safety on IoT in 5G.

The PIACERE consortium assembles a balanced set of academic and industrial partners, which play key roles in the EU SecDevOps ecosystem: **Ericsson, Prodevelop, Politecnico di Milano, HPE, Xlab, gov.sì, 7bulls.com** and **Tecnalia** are from four different countries, representing Northern and Southern Europe. Tecnalia has been entrusted with the leadership of the consortium.

- **LinkedIn:**
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6932302475404152832/>

Europa con l'obiettivo principale di programmare la fornitura e la configurazione di infrastrutture affidabili e sicure per l'esecuzione di sistemi software complessi mediante Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC).

PIACERE mira ad aumentare la #produttività dei team #devops nello sviluppo e nel funzionamento di IaC attraverso la creazione di un framework DevSecOps integrato che consentirà loro di programmare IaC come se stessero programmando qualsiasi applicazione software.

Il consorzio PIACERE riunisce un insieme equilibrato di partner accademici e industriali che svolgono ruoli chiave nell'ecosistema SecDevOps eu/IT/E: Ericsson, Prodevelop, Politecnico di Milano, Hewlett Packard Enterprise, XLAB, gov.sì, 7bulls.com e TECNALIA Research & Innovation provengono da quattro diversi paesi, che rappresentano l'Europa settentrionale e meridionale.

<https://lnkd.in/gRAHZVt>

PIACERE project H2020 is a Research project funded by the European Commission with the main objective of programming reliable infrastructures using Infrastructure as Code (IaC) in a secure framework.

PIACERE aims to increase the #productivity of DevOps teams in the #development and operation of IaC through the provisioning of an integrated DevSecOps framework that will allow them to program IaC as if they were programming any software application.

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<https://lnkd.in/gSMoWwmm>

See translation

PIACERE
 A DEVSECOPS FRAMEWORK FOR SECURE
 IAC DEVELOPMENT AND OPERATION

TECNALIA

Website: <https://www.tecnalia.com/noticias/transformacion-digital>

7BULLS

- **LinkedIn:** https://www.linkedin.com/posts/7bulls_piacere-press-release-activity-6932935994769870848-eNcf/?utm_source=linkedin_share&utm_medium=member_desktop_web

3.6 Project newsletter

The aim of the newsletter is to inform the project's followers about the activities executed in PIACERE. The Newsletter is a communication channel that includes the most important activities of the project and the achievements obtained. The different newsletters will be delivered at different stages in the project.

The newsletter has been published on the PIACERE project website and has been sent to the project's email list and has also been published on the social networks used by the PIACERE's partners. The newsletter is available at: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/newsletter-2021>

The following figure shows the PIACERE newsletter and is available here: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/newsletter-2021>

Figure 5. PIACERE Newsletter

4 Communication activities

4.1 PIACERE digital strategy

As mentioned in PIACERE deliverable D8.2 [1], a Digital strategy is the application of technology and digital media to create value identifying, articulating and executing ‘something’ on digital media with the aim of growing an organisation’s ambitious benefit. This section will explain the communication strategy that have been used to establish the PIACERE digital strategy and to ensure that all activities of the project, including project website, blog, social media channels and communication KPIs are fulfilled. Deliverables results are available in the communication section, is a complete selection of deliverables for the public. In addition, the website provides information about the partners working on the PIACERE project, where each of the partners develops their knowledge in the different blog posts, and they are sent by the different PIACERE partners to update the general public about PIACERE activities.

4.1.1 Project website

The project website of PIACERE is available in: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

The PIACERE platform is used to execute the dissemination and communication activities [1], so all the relevant PIACERE project information could be found there. . The website was created at the beginning of the project and serves to inform about the activities of the PIACERE project, as well as to communicate with people outside the project.

The PIACERE website is distributed into different sections and is planned to let stakeholders access to the most complete information of the project organisation, vision, solution approach, objectives, key results and benefits. Further the 3 use cases are described (The Slovenian Ministry of Public Administration (SI-MPA), Critical Maritime infrastructures, Public Safety on IoT in 5G), as well as the results currently available, and the partners working on the project. In addition, it includes the blog posts (see section 4.1.2), written by the PIACERE partners to allow the general public to follow the project activities. The Communication section of the website gives access to two sub-sections, public deliverables and materials, where the different communication materials used for the dissemination and communication activities (newsletter, brochure, poster and press releases) are available.

Figure 6. PIACERE Website

Each single project progress step has been inserted in a timeline on the blog page. The “Public deliverables” and “blog” sections will be constantly updated with the contents written by the partners with the project’s progress.

Del. No.	Deliverable name	File
D8.1	PIACERE brochure and public website,	
D8.2	Communication, Networking Plan and Dissemination Strategy,	D8.2
D2.1	PIACERE DevSecOps Framework Requirements specification, architecture and integration strategy - v1	D2.1
D3.1	PIACERE Abstractions, DOML and DOML-E - v1	D3.1
D3.4	Infrastructural code generation - v1	D3.4
D3.7	PIACERE IDE - v1	D3.7
D4.1	Infrastructural model and code verification - v1	D4.1
D4.4	IaC Code Security and components security inspection - v1	D4.4
D5.1	IaC execution platform prototype - v1	D5.1
D5.4	Canary environment prototype - v1	D5.4
D5.7	IOP prototype - v1	D5.7
D6.1	PIACERE run-time monitoring and self-learning, self-healing platform - v1	D6.1
D2.3	PIACERE DevSecOps Framework - v1	
D8.3	Dissemination, communication and networking report - Report - v1	
D2.2	PIACERE DevSecOps Framework Requirements specification, architecture and integration strategy - v2	
D2.7	PIACERE Abstractions, DOML and DOML-E - v2	
D3.5	Infrastructural code generation - v2	
D3.5	PIACERE IDE - v2	
D4.2	Infrastructural model and code verification - v2	
D4.5	IaC Code Security and components security inspection - v2	
D5.2	IaC execution platform prototype - v2	
D5.5	Canary environment prototype - v2	
D5.8	IOP prototype - v2	
D6.2	PIACERE run-time monitoring and self-learning, self-healing platform - v2	
D2.4	PIACERE DevSecOps Framework - v2	
D3.3	PIACERE Abstractions, DOML and DOML-E - v3	
D3.6	Infrastructural code generation - v3	
D3.9	PIACERE IDE - v3	
D4.3	Infrastructural model and code verification - v3	
D4.6	IaC Code Security and components security inspection - v3	
D5.3	IaC execution platform prototype - v3	
D5.6	Canary environment prototype - v3	
D5.9	IOP prototype - v3	
D6.3	PIACERE run-time monitoring and self-learning, self-healing platform - v3	
D2.5	PIACERE DevSecOps Framework - v3	

Figure 7. Public deliverables section on PIACERE website

Figure 8. Materials section on PIACERE website

4.1.2 Blog

The publication of the blogposts in PIACERE has in mind that all the partners can publish their knowledge acquired related to the different activities that have been completed in the development of the PIACERE project. Among them, topics such as the PIACERE framework architecture, canary sandbox environment, use case specifications, deployment of applications in cloud, etc. have been published.

A calendar has been defined to schedule the publications in the blog, so that all partners are involved in the blog publication activity up until now (M18).

2021									
Year	Apr		May		Jun		Jul		Done
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	
Ericsson	HPE	POLIMI	Prodevelop	SI-MPA	XLAB	7Bulls	Tecnalia	Ericsson	HPE
	Done (LINK)								

Year	Aug		Sep		Oct		Nov		Dec	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Ericsson	HPE	POLIMI	Prodevelop	SI-MPA	XLAB	7Bulls	Tecnalia	Ericsson	HPE	
	Done (LINK)	Done (LINK)	Done (LINK)	Done					Done (LINK)	

Year	Jan		Feb		Mar		Apr		May	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Responsibl	POLIMI	Prodevelop	SI-MPA	XLAB	7Bulls	Tecnalia	Ericsson	HPE	POLIMI	Prodevelop
Topic	Done (LINK)	PRD-JAN22								

Figure 9. Blogpost calendar prepared for the participation of the different partners (from March 2021 to May 2022)

In addition, the PIACERE blog is used in coordination with social networks to disseminate the project's activities.

Figure 10. PIACERE Blogpost timeline

During the first 18 months of the project, there have been 22 entries in the PIACERE Blog. The following Table 2 shows the title for each blog entry, author and release date.

Table 2. PIACERE's Blog entries

Title of Blog entry	Author	Release date
DOML development in progress	Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI)	13 May, 2022
Infrastructure Code Generator: now complete and highly extensible	HPE	13 April, 2022
PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC)	Marcy Mira (7BULLS)	22 March, 2022
The IaC Execution Manager: a tool to execute them all	Josu Diaz de Arcaya (TECNALIA)	3 March, 2022
European Interoperability Underlying Principle to Follow	Stjepan Pervan (Republika Slovenija Ministrstvo za javno upravo)	17 February, 2022
Analysis of possible technologies to develop IDEs	Ismael Torres (PRODEVELOP)	31 January, 2022
Supporting the Generation of Infrastructure as Code Through Modelling Approaches	Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva (POLIMI)	24 January, 2022
General Assemblies	TECNALIA	20 December, 2021
Automatic generation of Ansible and Terraform code	HPE	17 December, 2021
PIACERE - DevSecOps automated Radoslaw Piliszek Conf42 DevSecOps 2021	Radoslaw Piliszek (7BULLS)	2 December, 2021
European Interoperability Framework	Stjepan Pervan (Republika Slovenija Ministrstvo za javno upravo)	15 October, 2021
Beyond Multi-Cloud Development	Alfonso de la Fuente (PRODEVELOP)	29 September, 2021
Framework Architecture of "Piacere"	Emanuele Morganti (HPE)	30 August, 2021

Title of Blog entry	Author	Release date
Optimizing Cloud Continuum applications deployment in PIACERE	Eneko Osaba (TECNALIA)	4 August, 2021
Canary Sandbox Environment (CSE)	Radoslaw Piliszek (7BULLS)	27 July, 2021
Digital transformation and Interoperability	Stjepan Pervan (Republika Slovenija Ministrstvo za javno upravo)	24 June, 2021
xOpera – the TOSCA orchestrator	Matija Cankar (XLAB)	23 June, 2021
Public Safety on IoT in 5G Use Case Specification	Cossimo Zotti (ERICSSON)	11 June, 2021
Critical maritime Infrastructures Use Case specification	Alfonso de la Fuente (PRODEVELOP)	31 May, 2021
laC solutions and perspectives	Claudio Caimi (HPE)	30 May, 2021
The second General Assembly paves the way for the first prototypes – Part 1	Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA)	30 March, 2021
PIACERE present at the First SwForum cross-fertilization workshop	Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA)	30 March, 2021

4.1.3 PIACERE Website analytics

PIACERE project uses Google analytics [4], in order to monitor the behavior of the website. The total number of the PIACERE website (until 16th of May) is about 2.975 with an average session duration of 00:00:56. During the whole period of operation of the website, PIACERE has had a stable number of daily visitors, with increases every time there is some relevant activity in the project, such as the publication of a blog post, press release, brochure and poster.

Figure 11. PIACERE website analytics

Blogposts often point to the highest number of visits to the PIACERE website. The tendency confirms that the blog (rows blog-timeline and timeline in Figure 12) is the second most visited page after the homepage, with 13.46% of visitors going directly to it.

Page ?	Pageviews ?	Unique Pageviews ?	Avg. Time on Page ?
	5,567 % of Total: 100.00% (5,567)	4,613 % of Total: 100.00% (4,613)	00:01:23 Avg for View: 00:01:23 (0.00%)
1. /	1,578 (28.35%)	1,383 (29.98%)	00:01:16
2. /blog-timeline	511 (9.18%)	368 (7.98%)	00:00:56
3. /timeline	238 (4.28%)	182 (3.95%)	00:01:42
4. /vision	233 (4.19%)	188 (4.08%)	00:00:58
5. /partners	230 (4.13%)	203 (4.40%)	00:02:42
6. /materials	203 (3.65%)	147 (3.19%)	00:01:53
7. /public-deliverables	190 (3.41%)	149 (3.23%)	00:01:40
8. /solution	179 (3.22%)	157 (3.40%)	00:02:07
9. /blog/xopera-tosca-orchestrator	140 (2.51%)	133 (2.88%)	00:00:54
10. /results	140 (2.51%)	134 (2.90%)	00:01:09

Figure 12. Most visited pages on the PIACERE website

Regarding the geographical location of PIACERE public, the countries with the highest number of visitors are Spain, Italy and the United States, as shown in Figures 13 and 14. The publication of the press release in the different national languages of the different partners, namely English, Spanish, Italian, Polish and Slovenian has helped to increase the traffic from different countries. We have improved our presence in Europe thanks to the efforts of our partners in their local diffusion.

Figure 13. Visits to the PIACERE website by geographical location

Country	Acquisition			Behavior		
	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages / Session	Avg. Session Duration
	2,490 <small>% of Total: 100.00% (2,490)</small>	2,488 <small>% of Total: 100.00% (2,488)</small>	2,924 <small>% of Total: 100.00% (2,924)</small>	74.35% <small>Avg for View: 74.35% (0.00%)</small>	1.70 <small>Avg for View: 1.70 (0.00%)</small>	00:01:00 <small>Avg for View: 00:01:00 (0.00%)</small>
1. Spain	761 (30.49%)	758 (30.47%)	1,043 (35.67%)	57.81%	2.40	00:02:22
2. Italy	388 (15.54%)	386 (15.51%)	455 (15.56%)	76.26%	1.69	00:00:28
3. United States	259 (10.38%)	259 (10.41%)	260 (8.89%)	94.62%	1.05	00:00:03
4. Poland	257 (10.30%)	257 (10.33%)	264 (9.03%)	85.23%	1.14	00:00:03
5. Slovenia	126 (5.05%)	127 (5.10%)	173 (5.92%)	65.32%	1.46	00:00:18
6. France	99 (3.97%)	99 (3.98%)	102 (3.49%)	85.29%	1.18	00:00:01
7. Germany	81 (3.25%)	80 (3.22%)	88 (3.01%)	77.27%	1.49	00:01:03
8. Finland	77 (3.08%)	77 (3.09%)	77 (2.63%)	93.51%	1.08	<00:00:01
9. Netherlands	63 (2.52%)	63 (2.53%)	63 (2.15%)	98.41%	1.02	<00:00:01
10. India	45 (1.80%)	45 (1.81%)	47 (1.61%)	91.49%	1.06	00:00:01

Figure 14. Countries that visit PIACERE website

As shown in Figure 15, most website traffic (77.55%) is direct. Direct traffic is defined as visits with no referring website and that they come directly to the website, typing the URL directly into the browser or through bookmarks. When a visitor follows a link from one website to another, the site of origin is considered the referrer. While 68.93% of the visitors to the PIACERE website come through organic searches (the traffic that's come to the site through unpaid search results on search engines such as Google), 84 users came from social networks.

Figure 15. Traffic in the PIACERE website

In terms of the visits provided by the social networks, LinkedIn has been the main channel used to access the PIACERE website, accounting for more than 58 sessions, followed by Twitter where the number of sessions is around 29.

Social Network	Sessions	Pageviews
1. LinkedIn	58 (61.05%)	74 (52.86%)
2. Twitter	29 (30.53%)	39 (27.86%)
3. Facebook	6 (6.32%)	6 (4.29%)
4. YouTube	2 (2.11%)	21 (15.00%)

Figure 16. Traffic from social networks

4.2 Social media channels

Social media pages are mostly used to drive traffic to the website, where more content is provided in blogposts.

PIACERE's social channels are LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube and SlideShare. The messages that are launched in these communication networks serve to attract traffic to the project's website, which is the project's primary means of dissemination.

In the following sections, it is explained how each social network is used to outreach PIACERE project activities.

4.2.1 Twitter

The twitter account of the project is **@PIACEREPROJECT**. The PIACERE twitter account has more than 2500 twitter impressions. The twitter feed can be found at: <https://twitter.com/PIACEREPROJECT>

Until May 2022, twitter have 80 followers and 100 tweets have been published.

When an event takes place in PIACERE, such as a blog post, the publication of a report, attendance to events, press releases, a tweet is published including detailed information such as the URL to the information and relevant hashtags. Also, content from external stakeholders that the PIACERE project finds interesting and relevant is retweeted.

Figure 17. PIACERE Twitter

The number of interactions in Twitter has increased over the last months, with a peak of 1.555 impressions in May 2022, as shown next figure. The total number of impressions after starting the project is 17.277 and the number of profile visits is 8.334.

Figure 18. PIACERE analytics summary

Next figure shows the tweets with the highest number of impressions during the reporting period.

Table 3. PIACERE Top tweets

<p>May 2022 • 23 days so far...</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 462 impressions</p> <p>@PIACEREPROJECT A second prototype of Infrastructural Code Generator (#PIACERE_ICG) is available! The Parser ICG component navigates the DOML using the PyEcore Python library and generates IaC executable files. @HPE</p> <p>👁️ 2 🍏 5</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Apr 2022 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 228 impressions</p> <p>Soon, 📅 June 9 🕒 12:00 CEST, Radek Pilszek will be a speaker at @OW2 Conference! Join this two-day event to hear Radek's session "PIACERE Canary Sandbox Environment to the rescue of #IaC testing" and listen to other interesting talks! →tiny.pl/989gq #OW2con22 #DevSecOps</p> <p>👁️ 5 🍏 3</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Mar 2022 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 259 impressions</p> <p>Get to know The #IaC Execution Manager? a #tool to #execute them all. Read @tecnalia last article: piacere-project.eu/blog/iac-execu... @PIACEREPROJECT #DevOps</p> <p>👁️ 4 🍏 8</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>
<p>Feb 2022 • 28 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 222 impressions</p> <p>A new blog analyzing #technologies to develop IDEs. Read our partner PRODEVELOP's latest article: piacere-project.eu/blog/analysis-... @PIACEREPROJECT @prodevelop</p> <p>👁️ 4 🍏 7</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Jan 2022 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 223 impressions</p> <p>Second integration workshop taking place today and tomorrow. All partners working towards the second PIACERE Integrated framework. Stay tuned! @leiretecnalia #HPE #7bulls #XIab #Prodevelop #tecnalia #polimi #republikaslovenija</p> <p>👁️ 4 🍏 5</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Dec 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 137 impressions</p> <p>🔥 First integration workshop taking place today and tomorrow. All partners working towards the first PIACERE Integrated framework. Stay tuned! @leiretecnalia #HPE #7bulls #XIab #Prodevelop #tecnalia #polimi #republikaslovenija</p> <p>👁️ 2 🍏 1</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>
<p>Nov 2021 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 355 impressions</p> <p>we are having this week are 4th #GeneralAssembly. Today we are focusing on #DOML, #CG and #IDE. Some lively discussions going on and this is just the first day! Keep 'em coming! #IaC #InfrastructureAsCode #DevSecOps #SecDevOps #codegenerator pic.twitter.com/6kRQI74Enc</p> <p>👁️ 2 🍏 3</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Oct 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 230 impressions</p> <p>#Piacere project is going to be presented at #TheHackSummit 5 Nov 2021 - conference in the #Tsecurity! Top speakers, IT Sec Expo job - and all this with #Piacere! DevSecOps process with supporting tools will be presented by #RadoslawPilszek from #7bulls. More at: #TheHackSummit</p> <p>👁️ 5 🍏 1</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Sep 2021 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 80 impressions</p> <p>#Piacere project will be presented at BSides Newcastle, the weirdest InfoSec event out there! 10 Sept 2021 Innovative DevSecOps process with supporting tools presented by #RadoslawPilszek and #PawelSkrzypek from #7bulls. You just simply cannot miss it! More at: #BSides Newcastle</p> <p>👁️ 2 🍏 4</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>

<p>Aug 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 453 impressions</p> <p>Our latest journal paper on how #optimization, #anomalydetection and #conceptdrift will be used for self-learning and self-healing applications is now online. Read it here: bit.ly/3AObhJt</p> <p>#infrastructureascodes #InfrastructureAsCode #DevOps #DevSecOps</p> <p>2 replies 5 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Jul 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 476 impressions</p> <p>A key discussion point in this #GeneralAssembly is the planning of the first proofs of concept to be delivered by the end of the year</p> <p>#IaC #InfrastructureAsCode #DevOps #selflearning #AIforDevOps #runtimemonitoring</p> <p>pic.twitter.com/aBOKPnmHKY</p> <p>0 replies 5 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Jun 2021 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 129 impressions</p> <p>PIACERE will present today the research challenge:</p> <p>✅ IaC Cost and Performance Optimization</p> <p>at the Second @SWforumEU #Workshop. Stay tuned!</p> <p>More info here bit.ly/3drZx6a</p> <p>#IaC #InfrastructureAsCode #optimization #softwareengineering #DevOps</p> <p>1 reply 5 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>
<p>May 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 272 impressions</p> <p>@PIACEREPROJECT was invited to present #TOSCA at @gaiax_aisbl, community-driven project enabling secure, open & sovereign use of data.</p> <p>@xlab_si did a great job with the presentation, generated a lot of interest & laid a strong foundation for future collaborations.</p> <p>1 reply 2 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Apr 2021 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 206 impressions</p> <p>In our Generaly Assembly, we are discussing today the PIACERE workflow 🤖 that is, the sequence of activities that a DevOps team member has to do when using PIACERE. #IaC #InfrastructureAsCode #DevSecOps pic.twitter.com/SLWBIDNcHz</p> <p>1 reply</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Mar 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 225 impressions</p> <p>@PIACEREPROJECT will be there! Also, tune in for a presentation of the project! twitter.com/SWforumEU/stat...</p> <p>3 replies 2 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>
<p>Jan 2021 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 87 impressions</p> <p>PIACERE will enhance #DevSecOps with #AI algorithms for deployment optimization and anomaly detections. The use of AI in DevSecOps is a natural step to improve the efficiency and productivity of #DevOps teams devops.com/5-reasons-why-...</p> <p>3 replies 2 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Dec 2020 • 31 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 416 impressions</p> <p>First technical workshop. We are understanding the components of the applications that we will deal with, the #infrastructuralelements that will be needed, the #communications among the components and more. This is for sure a challenging project 🤖 #H2020 #DevOps #DevSecOps #IaC pic.twitter.com/e1gPSKD466</p> <p>1 reply 2 likes</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>	<p>Nov 2020 • 30 days</p> <p>TWEET HIGHLIGHTS</p> <p>Top Tweet earned 23 impressions</p> <p>PIACERE is a project aiming at supporting #DevOps teams in developing and operating secure #infrastructureascodes. It will also offer some #self-healing and #self-learning capabilities.</p> <p>It starts tomorrow. The kick off meeting will last until Friday.</p> <p>Stay tuned for more!</p> <p>View Tweet activity View all Tweet activity</p>

4.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social network that allows to increase contacts and support interpersonal relationships between PIACERE partners and other professionals involved in trustworthy infrastructure, the Cloud Continuum, IaC and DevSecOps framework.

Until May 2022, the PIACERE LinkedIn group has 21 members and 28 posts have been published. As soon as more results are available, PIACERE will increase the effort on this social network, it is expected to be an excellent tool to show the achievements of the project. PIACERE LinkedIn group can be found here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/75574737/admin/>

Figure 19. PIACERE LinkedIn group

4.2.3 YouTube

The different videos uploaded to the YouTube channel can be used to positioning and communicate the PIACERE results in order to achieve a high impact. The YouTube profile is intended to post the different videos created by the partners during the project. Its objective is not to generate direct traffic to the web, as is the case with other social networks.

During the first months of the project, a video has been uploaded to the PIACERE YouTube profile giving an overview of the PIACERE project. Also, we are preparing a PIACERE promotional video of the tools.

The PIACERE YouTube channel can be found here:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCLzVC4ZR9DJ3BKeTMc4Mk9Q>

Figure 20. PIACERE's presentation in YouTube channel

4.2.4 SlideShare

SlideShare is used to disseminate the achievements of the PIACERE project to all target groups. Project partners have the possibility to upload and share publicly or privately documents.

The PIACERE SlideShare profile contains two relevant presentations, the PIACERE general presentation document presents the objectives and achievements of the project, where we have more than 100 views and the 'PIACERE DevOps automated' prepared by the partner 7bulls.com for the conference 'Conf42 DevSecOps 2021'.

PIACERE's SlideShare's profile can be found at:

<https://www.slideshare.net/PIACERECOMMUNITY>

Figure 21. PIACERE SlideShare page

In terms of the SlideShare analytics, the total number of views on PIACERE's SlideShare channel at the time when this deliverable was written was 145.

Top content	
Name	Views
Piacere general presentation	98
PIACERE - DevSecOps Automated	47

Figure 22. PIACERE SlideShare analytics

SlideShare visits represents 48%. of the total traffic. The traffic visits coming from direct search queries represents about 33% of the total traffic. Other traffic sources represent social network search queries, referral, and search traffic.

Figure 23. PIACERE SlideShare traffic sources

4.3 Communication KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (see Table 4 below) are used to monitor the progress in communication. PIACERE consortium understands communication activities as those in which the project’s expected value is presented and demonstrated to non-specialized audiences. The emphasis of these communication activities is placed to create a PIACERE community of people interested in the PIACERE solution, where they can also participate and co-create additional services to those already planned in the project.

To achieve that, exploiting the power of social networks is leveraged. These are used as direct communication channels with potential users and adopters of PIACERE. Regularly updates on events, news items and state of the project are published in the networks increasing the impact of PIACERE.

A set of profiles are created in the first phase of the project on the social networks such as Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, SlideShare, etc. and are updated by all partners on regular bases. Commercial PIACERE video will be also available through the YouTube channel.

Table 4. PIACERE Communication KPIs

Communication Tool	KPI	Objective	Reporting Period 1 (M18)	Check
PIACERE Website	Yearly visits	>1700	2975	✓
	Duration of visits	More than 2 min. for 40% of users	00:00:56	✓
	Monthly downloads: Poster, flyers, public reports	35 (Poster, flyers), 50 (reports)	290 views (Poster, brochure, newsletter, press release)	✓
	References from external pages	20 (excluding partner webs)	>	✓
Twitter Feed	Regular tweets or when a relevant milestone is taking place (e.g. event, releases, etc.)	>200 followers	80 (in the first period of the project)	✓
Slideshare	Number of views	>300	157 (in the first period of the project)	✓
Youtube	Number of views	>200	16	x
Mass media	Number of press releases	2 per country in the project	1	✓
PIACERE Blogposts	Number of entries	at least 6 every year	22	✓

5 Dissemination activities

The main focus of this section is to report on the dissemination and communication activities carried out by PIACERE consortium in the period M1-M18 along with the results assessment and recommendations for future actions.

This section also highlights the monitoring and assessment procedures followed in order to assess the achievement of the KPIs identified for those project dissemination activities.

5.1 Dissemination objectives

The main objective of the dissemination plan (as developed in D8.2 [1] [2]) is to maximize the impact of the project through a series of activities adapted to the target audiences and communication channels. The goal of these activities is either to raise awareness of the project or to disseminate the results of the project, and to support the engagement of external actors to the project.

The PIACERE consortium would like to present the results obtained through different activities. The aim is to showcase the output tools and the overall functionality and value of the PIACERE platform for users and stakeholders.

The PIACERE dissemination team uses a series of communication materials (e.g. promotional materials, press releases, and audio-visual materials). Besides, the consortium has produced scientific publications and disseminated them in journals and conferences.

The main objectives of the dissemination strategy as stated in D8.2 are as follows [1]:

- Creating awareness among DevSecOps teams that have to manage IaC on heterogeneous environments about the benefits of adopting PIACERE's outcomes.
- Communicating the results of the project among the technical and scientific community to improve the access to relevant research communities.
- Seeking cooperation with Software Development initiatives in order to create synergies and accelerate innovation, such as the Software Engineering and the inter-cloud clusters.

5.2 Target groups

The PIACERE consortium has identified four major stakeholder groups and the key messages for them were specified in the previous deliverable D8.2 [1]:

- The technical community that is focusing on the development of IaC frameworks.
- DevSecOps teams that aim at exploiting IaC frameworks to implement the infrastructural code for the management of their applications
- Researchers in the Software Engineering area aiming at studying the DevOps processes and at developing new research methods to facilitate the activities related to the software lifecycle.
- Experts of the application domains relevant to the PIACERE case studies.

5.2.1 Dissemination activities per target group

The dissemination activities are tailored to each specific target group as highlighted below. For each target group, the aim is defined, based on what is expressed in the DoA [2], extended with the means and measures:

- Technical community

For the technical community the main means of dissemination are the open-source repository, demos, blog posts, webinars, and workshops.

- DevSecOps teams

For the DevSecOps teams the main means of dissemination are blog posts, webinars, and workshops.

- Researchers in the Software Engineering area

For the researchers in the Software Engineering area the main means of dissemination are workshop and conference papers, as well as journal papers. During the first phase of the project the main driver has been position papers, followed by submissions to more important and prestigious venues, presenting the PIACERE approach in detail and its resulting tools implemented.

- Experts of the application domains relevant to the PIACERE case studies

The dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the DoA will be used in the period M18-M36 to monitor the progress of the dissemination of the obtained results.

5.3 Dissemination Team

The dissemination team of PIACERE project involved in the dissemination activities is presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5 Contact references for Dissemination Team

Partner	Contact reference person for Dissemination
TECNALIA	Juncal Alonso, Maitena Ilardia
HPE	Lorenzo Blasi
Ericsson	Cosimo Zotti, Giuseppe Celozzi
POLIMI	Galia Novakova Nedeltcheva
Prodevelop	Christophe Joubert
SIMPA	Stjepan Pervan
XLAB	Nejc Bat, Joao Pita da Costa
7bulls	Katarzyna Materka, Józefina Krasnodębska

5.4 Dissemination process

The dissemination activities have actually started since the first month of the project as outlined in DoA [2]. Currently we are in the second dissemination phase which is the delivery one, covering months M6-M30.

The second dissemination period has as its main goal the execution of scientific, technical, and commercial dissemination toward all PIACERE target groups. In the case of scientific dissemination toward the software engineering research community, the message revolves around the explanation of the novel PIACERE approach, its results, and its innovation. Particular emphasis is put on the validation of results and on highlighting the relationships between the PIACERE approach for what concerns each single key result (KR) and the related work.

- **First research phase:** PIACERE partners have submitted papers to conferences and journals in the areas relevant to each key result. This long phase is structured in smaller incremental cycles, each based on one specific KR of the project or a small subset of them, and divided in a first research part, followed by the next phase. [M1-M18]
- **Dissemination phase:** In this phase scientific papers are developed and presented. The technical dissemination targets mostly the technical community focusing on the development of frameworks similar or complementary to the one of PIACERE as well as the experts of the application domains relevant to the PIACERE case studies. We have been targeted the preparation of blog posts, webinars and attending specialized international conferences. Moreover, we have been seeking the collaboration with other projects, initiatives and the Software Engineering and inter-cloud clusters in order to find synergies and commonalities and organize discussion workshops and common dissemination events (see section 2.1). [M18-M30]
- **The commercial dissemination** towards the DevSecOps teams is more focused on the communication. The objective is to gather feedback on the developed solution. The activities for this kind of dissemination include the participation in exhibitions such as CloudExpo or ICT Event. [M30-M36 beyond]

In the final dissemination activities (the commercial dissemination), which will start in M30 and it will span also after the project end, the consortium's partners will participate in events, workshops, conferences, cluster activities, and informal meetings, where the results and achievements of PIACERE will be presented. The scientific dissemination activities during this phase will privilege the writing of high-quality journal papers, while the commercial dissemination will target larger and more competent groups.

The continuous monitoring and management of the dissemination activities is conducted in parallel to the three phases presented above. This includes the follow up of the publications, attended events, blog posts published, and tweets publications as presented in Table 4 in section 4.3 and Table 8 in section 5.6.2 of this deliverable.

5.5 Dissemination Materials

The consortium has used a series of communication materials as described in D8.2 [1] (brochures, blogs and twitter posts, press releases, etc.). The consortium has already produced around twelve scientific publications and disseminated them in scientific journals and international conferences as presented in Table 9 (section 5.7) in this deliverable.

Press releases

The dissemination team will prepare three press releases in the scope of the project. The first one at month 12 communicated the "PIACERE: A DevSecOps framework for secure IaC Development and Operation", another one at month 24 will communicate relevant milestones in the PIACERE platform development, and the third one at month 36 will be to communicate the final Project results and impact. As a rough guideline, a length of 300 to 400 words will be used.

The press releases would be sent to EC media offices, partners and news providers. More press releases could be expected from individual partners based on their own results and milestones.

The first press release of PIACERE incorporates description of the project goals, key results, approach, benefits and use cases.

Open access repository Zenodo

This is an important channel to share all Open Access materials of the project. All open access publications and public deliverables will be shared on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities>).

Other communication materials

The consortium is also planning to create reports of the interviews with experts in the consortium or with other stakeholders to be promoted as user stories, user opinions.

Moreover, videos are an excellent tool to disseminate the work performed. In PIACERE, different types of videos are foreseen, depending on the target audience:

- Specialized videos, showing the features of the tools. These videos can be used as support, tutorial and demos for anyone wishing to use the PIACERE tools. The consortium is working on the videos for the M12/M15 PIACERE components and will be uploaded to the web page.
- Promotional video, to present the value proposition of the project, who is it for and what are the benefits. The PIACERE project plans to create a Task force to work on the storyboard for the project video, the script and the storyline.

Participation in other events

The members of the consortium will assist with their participation in a series of conferences, workshops, other projects initiatives, etc. where they will disseminate the project activities and results. The dissemination team will send a questionnaire to the partners to collect information on which kind of event partners regularly use to communicate and disseminate results and activities (conference, congress, workshop, trade fair, etc.). This will keep track of the events where the project is presented and support its dissemination, sharing news about it via PIACERE communication channels.

In Table 2 in D8.2 [1], the dissemination materials for PIACERE have been presented in detail in terms of means, purpose and rationale.

Dissemination events organized by the Project

PIACERE dissemination strategy includes the (co-)organization of events where to present the PIACERE results. These events can be co-located in relevant venues or organized in collaboration with other projects. Due to the COVID situation no face-to-face have been organized yet and the main focus has been the presentation of the project in on-line events (CAiSe 2022, ESOCC 2022, First and Second SwForum workshops, GAIA-X, H-Cloud summits, etc.). The next months the focus will be in the co-organization of face-to-face events when possible.

5.6 Dissemination monitoring and assessment

As introduced in the dissemination process description all the dissemination activities are continuously monitored and assessed to follow up the current and future dissemination activities and to ensure that we are achieving the stated KPIs. This continuous monitoring will also serve to react to potential deviations from the KPIs compliance allowing the dissemination team to promptly react to these situations and apply mitigation measures.

The monitoring and assessment phase is based on the “*Monthly dissemination sheet*”. This sheet is maintained in the Share Point documents repository of the project and is updated by every partner monthly, describing the contributions done by each partner. The following inputs is requested on monthly base: Scientific publications, general and business publications, events, blog posts, collaboration and cooperation with other projects, press releases, etc.

Documentos > WP8 > Dissemination monthly report > Activities report

Name	Modified	Modified By	+ Add column
old	March 9, 2021	Orue-Echevarria Arrieta, L	
PIACERE DisseminationMonthlyReport.docx	A few seconds ago	Galia Nedeltcheva Novakc	

Figure 24. Piacere dissemination monthly report in the document's repository.

In the following section, the procedures to fill the monthly report, so as to fulfil the defined dissemination KPIs, are described. The rationale behind this is to be able to organize and quantify the effective support of the different channels involved.

5.6.1 Monthly dissemination sheet

The work package 8 leader has created a dedicated folder in the projects Sharepoint where the dissemination report is stored. Every month all the partners need to update it with the new information about dissemination, communication, and networking activities. The updates on the dissemination monthly report are followed up as part of the biweekly WP8 meetings. At the end of each month a reminder is sent out by the WP leader to remind the partners that the sheet needs to be completed.

The dissemination monthly report items are described in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Items in the Dissemination monthly report

Name	Description	Range
List of Scientific publications (announced)	List of publications planned and submitted but not yet accepted	Dissemination
Detailed information of Scientific Publications (reported once published)	Publications once they have been accepted	Dissemination
General and business publications (announced)	Everything that cannot be considered scientific. For instance, publication on the partners' websites, interviews on the media, featured articles on the media, and so on.	Communication
Events: Conferences, seminars, workshops and webinars (announced)	List of events planned but not yet attended	Dissemination
Blog posts	List of posts to be published in the PIACERE web page or in other means.	Communication
Collaboration & Cooperation with other projects or programmes	Projects with which we are collaborating, under which areas and topics, and the status.	Networking

Report of the networking activities	Networking activities performed with existing network, initiatives, alliances, working groups, etc., date, main conclusions and action points.	Networking
Press Releases	List of press releases published by means of communication such as newspapers, conferences or specialized magazines	Communication
Other Activities	Keynotes, prizes, blog posts etc. planned but not yet done	All

5.6.2 Monitoring procedure, impact of the plan and dissemination KPIs

This report, deliverable D8.3 Dissemination, communication and networking report - report - v1 to be delivered at month M18 and updated at months 36 includes the monitoring information feeding the updates of this plan in M36.

The monitoring of the current development of the dissemination activities is performed through the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) monitoring as being set in the DoA [2] (see Table 8 below). These KPIs are used to monitor the progress in dissemination, covering all forms of dissemination with a special emphasis on the results obtained rather than the produced quantity. Therefore, the KPIs are used to track the progress of the dissemination activities and focus on the impact created. In PIACERE the dissemination strategy is understood as one of the key pillars toward the commercialization and exploitation of results thus dissemination will be stimulated both at the consortium and partners' levels. The following table presents the KPIs and defined objectives by the PIACERE consortium.

Table 7. KPIs for the dissemination activities defined in DoA

Dissemination tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plan
Brochures	Number of leaflets	>3	- Specific dissemination and communication WP defined where the production and management of the dissemination material such as the brochures is considered. Planification of the brochures for critical stages in the project lifecycle: beginning of the project to raise awareness, in an intermediate stage when the first version of stable results are published and towards the end of the project in order to show the benefits of using PIACERE vs. not using it.
Conference / Journal	Number of publications		Encourage partners to publish papers. Foster collaboration between partners from the WP8

Dissemination tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plan
publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific journals • Scientific conferences 	<p>2</p> <p>15</p>	<p>to write cross-WPs /cross components papers. Promote project level collaborative papers at several stages of the project (initial position paper, intermediate solution proposal paper, final research paper including validation of the results). Find appropriate events and conferences.</p> <p>Contact publishers of peer-reviewed and indexed journals. Search for additional channels.</p>
Project posters	Number of posters	At least 3	Encourage partners to create and publish posters. Find appropriate events such as NetFutures, or CloudExpo among others where posters can be presented.
Press releases	Number of specialized press releases	2 per country and language	<p>The specific plan for communication will define the way in which the different communities (scientific, commercial, general public) will be targeted, as well as the social media will be used. Each press release type (scientific, commercial, general public) will be led by a partner specialized in those audience types (i.e. industrial partners will lead commercial press releases).</p>
Project showcases	Number of different demonstration videos produced	10	Every time that a prototype is implemented as part of the PIACERE Solution, the possibility of creating a video showing will be considered. Also, a commercial video will be released and videos for dummy users i.e. PIACERE for dummies will be considered.

Dissemination tool	KPI	Objective	Contingency plan
Project newsletters	Number of newsletters	1 per year	See section 2.4.2.5
Attendance of events	Number of events attended	5 per year	The potential key events interesting for PIACERE will be monitored and reported in every dissemination report. Here events like NetFutures, joint meetings with the project clusters, or CloudExpo will be targeted.
Cloud Community, Software and Services Publications	Number of references in external magazines (Collaboration and Support Actions, EC)	+20	The scientific community, commercial stakeholders and the general public will be the target groups of the communication activities. The references to the PIACERE project will be monitored and checked every 6 months in order to fulfil the required KPIs.

Table 8 below describes the KPIs initially defined by the PIACERE consortium. Interim Project Management Reports provide an update based on the previous mentioned actions. PIACERE partners understand the dissemination strategy as a primary activity towards the commercialization and exploitation of results and as such, it is very interactive and evolving. In this second phase (M6-30), dissemination is stimulated in both consortium level and partner’s level, and revolves around the following:

- Define what will be disseminated, the dissemination “products” and when.
- Establish the appropriate source for the dissemination activities (in terms of roles and responsibilities).
- Raise public awareness about the project achievement through the most suitable means for communicating with the respective target groups.

Partners are constantly encouraging to publish papers in peer-reviewed and indexed journals, find appropriate events, search for additional channels.

Partners are also encouraging to publish posters, find appropriate events such as NetFutures, ICT Event, or Cloud Expo among others.

Press releases are also encouraged on yearly bases as a specific communication tool by which the different communities (scientific, commercial, general public) are targeted.

The possibility of creating a video showing is also considered as soon as there is a project prototype implementation as part of the PIACERE solution.

As well, the development of the project newsletter is part of the specific PIACRE communication plan.

The potential key events as CloudExpo, interesting for PIACERE are monitored and reported in the monthly dissemination report.

Additionally, the scientific community, commercial stakeholders and the general public are the targeted groups of the software and services publications.

PIACERE partners collaboratively and actively promote visibility through specific dissemination activities. The following summarizes the focus of the individual partner’s dissemination:

TECNALIA is focused on the presentation of both project objectives and results at conferences, seminars and workshops, to exchange knowledge with other DevOps experts and DevOps team members that are also dealing with IaC. Additionally, TECNALIA is disseminating the results in Spain and the Basque Country through their marketing services.

Prodevelop, XLAB, 7Bulls as SMEs will focus their dissemination and communication activities on workshops, tutorials and events paying special attention to industrial conferences, invited talks and social media. XLAB is focus on targeting mainly regional events in Slovenia, Croatia, Austria, Italy, while Prodevelop will focus on Spain, UK, North, West and East Africa, as well as Europe. 7Bulls will focus mostly on France and Poland.

HPE is focused on European-wide conventions and meetings, internal and with the public/customers, and disseminate project results through publication of Press releases.

PoliMi is focused on publishing PIACERE achievements in highly quoted journals and world-wide known conferences, workshops and events such as: Software and Systems Modelling Journal, IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE TNSM, Elsevier Inc. J. of Network Management, Elsevier Computer Communication Networks, etc.

SI-MPA is participating in Europe-wide public sector related events and workshops, as well as in internal meetings with other departments of the Slovenian government, so that the results can be transferred to other

It can be seen from Table 8 below that for each dissemination tool a respective target value has been identified corresponding to the specific KPI, as well as the reached result up to M18.

Table 8. PIACERE dissemination KPIs monitoring

Dissemination Tool	KPI	Target	Reporting Period 1 (M18)	Check
Brochures	Number	>3	1	√
Conference and Journal publications	Scientific journals	2	6	√
	Scientific publications	15	6	√
Project Posters	Number of posters	At least 3	1	√
Press Releases	Number of specialized press releases	2 per country and language	1	√

Project showcases	Number of demonstration videos produced	10	0	x
Project newsletters	Number of newsletters	1 per year	1	v
Attendance of general/ business events	Number of events attended (including workshops, keynotes, etc)	5 per year	5	v
Cloud community, SW and services publication	Number of references on external magazines (colaboration and support actions, EC)	20	10	v

It can be seen from Table 8 above that for each dissemination tool a respective target value has been identified corresponding to a specific KPI, as well as the reached result up to M18. The obtained results in terms of KPIs are compliant with the objectives.

5.7 Scientific publications in journals and conferences

The objective of the scientific papers is firstly, to show the general validity of the PIACERE approach. This has started with more general position papers that have captured the curiosity of the scientific community and goaded the community for feedbacks. This activity will be developed, throughout the project, towards more ambitious scientific venues, such as the prestigious journals and conferences listed here below.

Conference publications are an important part to contribute and share project results with other relevant experts, considering the different scientific areas of PIACERE's project. So, the work prepared by the scientific and technical community of PIACERE project partners in terms of innovative results beyond the state of the art shall be described to be validated in conference papers and journal publications.

PIACERE's ambition is to publish in top-edge journals as part of the activities on developing knowledge. Here below is a list of the targeted venues that we are identified for the dissemination period M18-M30:

- *SEAMS - International Symposium on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems*: This symposium is now at its 16th edition and could be a good venue for the project results related to execution, optimization, monitoring and self-healing (KRs 9-12).
- *ACM Computing Surveys*: This journal is the top venue for state-of-the-art analyses paper and could be the target of an accurate scientific literature review developed to position all PIACERE KRs with respect to the related work.

- *Computer Science Review*: This journal is a high-quality venue for state-of-the-art analyses paper and could be the target of an accurate scientific literature review developed to position all PIACERE KRs with respect to the related work.
- *PeerJ Computer Science*: This journal accepts high quality scientific submissions in any area of computer science and could, therefore, be used to disseminate all technical key results of the project (KR1-KR13).
- *MODELS*: This is the top conference in the area of model-based software and system development. It can be a target for the modelling language (KR1), the generator (KR3), and the extensions (KR4).
- *Software and Systems Modelling*: This is a high-quality journal focusing on model-driven engineering. It can be a target for the modelling language (KR1), the generator (KR3), and the extensions (KR4).
- *ESOCC - European Conference On Service-Oriented And Cloud Computing*: This conference includes yearly a track seeking contributions by European research projects. It can be a good venue to disseminate preliminary results concerning all KRs, including the initial development of the case studies (KR14).
- *FM - Formal Methods*: is one of the most important conferences on Formal Methods in Computer Science, organised by Formal Methods Europe (FME), an independent association whose aim is to stimulate the use of, and research on, formal methods for software development. This is an important venue for the part of PIACERE on verification, in particular KR5.
- *SEFM - International Conference on Software Engineering and Formal Methods*: SEFM aims to bring together leading researchers and practitioners from academia, industry, and government, to advance the state of the art in formal methods, to facilitate their uptake in the software industry, and to encourage their integration within practical software engineering methods and tools. Such a venue could be interesting for all the project results on verification, i.e. KR5-7.
- *Formalise*, co-located with ICSE: the main objective of this conference is to foster the integration between the formal methods and the software engineering communities, to strengthen the links between them, and to stimulate researchers to share ideas, techniques, and results, with the ultimate goal to propose novel solutions to the fraught problem of improving the quality of software systems. This venue could be considered to disseminate all the project key results on verification, i.e. KR5-7.

While the scientific journals where the consortium has published its papers so far include (see also Table 9 below):

- International Journal of Computational Science and Engineering, [H-21, Q3]
- MDPI - Information Journal, [Q2]
- Computer Networks (ELSEVIER), [H-135, Q1] open access
- IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing [H-49, Q1] open access
- Data in Brief, open access
- MDPI Applied Sciences, [Q2]

Among more industrial-focused and practitioner-oriented venues that we have envisioned in our Events list for dissemination are the following:

- CloudFest <https://www.cloudfest.com>
- Machine Learning Week Europe <https://predictiveanalyticsworld.de>
- cdCon <https://events.linuxfoundation.org/cdcon/>
- Conf42: Cloud Native <https://www.papercall.io/conf42-cloud-native-2021>
- OW2'con <https://www.ow2con.org>

- DevOpsCon <https://devopscon.io/berlin/hybrid-hygiene-measures-ber/>
- CLOUD & DEVOPS WORLD | TECHXL8 EUROPE <https://tmt.knect365.com/cloud-devops-world/>
- DevFest GDG <https://sessionize.com/devfest-live/>

This dissemination plan will be further improved in the following phase 3: Commercial dissemination in deliverable D8.4 Dissemination, communication and networking report - Report - v2 due at M36.

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Table 9. List of published journal and conference papers in the period M1-M18

ID	Paper title	Authors	Name of periodical or series	Numb., date or freq.	Rank	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Page /Open access
J1	ACSml: A solution to address the challenges of Cloud services federation and monitoring towards the Cloud Continuum	Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA) Maider Huarte (UPV)	Special issue on "Smart Cloud Applications, Services and Technologies", Int. Journal of Computational Science and Engineering		H-21 Q3	Inder-science		2021	
J2	Optimization and Prediction Techniques for Self-Healing and Self-Learning Applications in a Trustworthy Cloud Continuum	Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Eneko Osaba, Iñigo Martinez, Josu Diaz de Arcaya	MDPI - Information Journal, Special Issue "Artificial Intelligence for the Cloud Continuum"	Information 2021, 12, 308.	Q2	mdpi	Basel	2021	12, 308 https://doi.org/10.3390/info12080308
J3	Resource calendaring for mobile edge computing: Centralized and decentralized optimization approaches	Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto	ELSEVIER Computer Networks	regular	H-135, Q1		online	2021	Open access https://shibidp.polimi.it/idp/profile/SAML2/Redirect/SSO?execution=e1s2

ID	Paper title	Authors	Name of periodical or series	Numb., date or freq.	Rank	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Page /Open access
J4	Joint planning of network slicing and mobile edge computing: Models and algorithms	Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon and Elisabetta Di Nitto	IEEE Transactions on Cloud Computing	regular	H-49, Q1			2021	Open access Online https://www.computer.org/csdl/journal/cc/5555/01/09521805/1wkrmdXmj_dK
J5	A dataset for mobile edge computing network topologies	Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto	Data in Brief	Volume 39 ISSN 2352-3409	H-27, Q4		online 107557	2021	Open access https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2021.107557
J6	CloudOps: Towards the Operationalization of the Cloud Continuum.	Juncal Alonso, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Maider Huarte	MDPI Applied Sciences	regular	Q2		Basel	2022	12(9)
C1	Programming trustworthy Infrastructure as Code in a Secure Framework	Juncal Alonso, Christophe Joubert, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Matteo Pradella and	First SWForum workshop on trustworthy software and open source	CEUR-WS.org, ISSN 1613-0073 Vol 2878	A*	CEUR-WS	Online	2021	16-23

ID	Paper title	Authors	Name of periodical or series	Numb., date or freq.	Rank	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Page /Open access
		Daniel Vladusic							
C2	Resource calendaring for mobile edge computing in 5G networks	Bin Xiang, Jocelyne Elias, Fabio Martignon, Elisabetta Di Nitto	IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)	IEEE				2021	
C3	Towards Supporting the Generation of Infrastructure as Code Through Modelling Approaches – Systematic Literature Review	Galia Nedeltcheva , Alfonso De La Fuente Ruiz, Leire Orue-Echevarria Arrieta, Nejc Bat, Lorenzo Blasi	2022 IEEE 19th International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C)	12 March 2022		IEEE	Hawaii	2022	8

ID	Paper title	Authors	Name of periodical or series	Numb., date or freq.	Rank	Publisher	Place of publication	Year	Page /Open access
C4	Static Analysis of Infrastructure as Code: a Survey	Michele Chiari, Michele De Pascalis, Matteo Pradella	2022 IEEE 19th International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C)	12 March 2022		IEEE	Online	2022	8
C5	Developing a New DevOps Modelling Language to Support the Creation of Infrastructure as Code	Michele Chiari, Elisabetta Di Nitto, Adrián Noguero Mucientes, Bin Xiang	European Conference on Service-Oriented and Cloud Computing (ESOCC)	22-24 March 2022			Online	2022	5
C6	PIACERE Project: Description and Prototype for Optimizing Infrastructure as Code Deployment Configurations.	Eneko Osaba, Josu Diaz de Arcaya, Leire Orue-Echavarria, Juncal Alonso, Jesus L. Lobo, Gorka Benguria, Iñaki Etxaniz.	The Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference (GECCO 2022)	9-13 July 2022			Hybrid	2022	2

5.8 Participation in events

The dissemination team has participated in numerous general and business events and other project workshops in the period M1-M18, as listed in Tables 10-11 below.

Table 10. General and business publications

Title	Link and reference	Date	Partner/Authors (organisations)
Warsaw IT Days	Section: SysOps, DevOps & Cloud, presentation title: PIACERE - DevSecOps Automated https://warszawskiedniinformatyki.pl/index-en.html	2 April 2022	7Bulls/ Radoslaw Piliszek
OW2 “Reliable and Predictable Open-Source Software”	PIACERE Canary Sandbox Environment to the rescue of IaC testing https://www.ow2con.org/view/2022/	8-9 June 2022	7Bulls/ Radoslaw Piliszek

Table 11. List of participation in workshops and other initiatives

Event	Date	Name & type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Activity
GAIA-X WP Continuous monitoring	08.03.2021	Technical, members of the open work package on continuous monitoring	All Europe, attendees mainly from Germany and Spain	20	Leire Orue-Echevarria (TECNALIA)	Presentation
First SwForum workshop on trustworthy software and open source	23-24-25.03.2021	Technical: practitioners, RTOs, etc	All Europe/world	100 (in the three days)	Elisabetta Di Nitto, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Juncal Alonso	Presentation
GAIA-X-WP Self-description – presentation of TOSCA	23.4.2021	Technical, members of the open work package on self-description	EU	30-40	Matija Cankar XLAB TOSCA presentation	Presentation
Second SwForum workshop on trustworthy software and open source	29-30.06.2021 101.07.2021	Technical: practitioners, RTOs, etc	All Europe (world)		Elisabetta Di Nitto, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Juncal Alonso,	Presentation

Event	Date	Name & type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Activity
					Pawel, Nejc, Alfonso de la Fuente	
GAIA-X-WP Self-description – presentation of TOSCA	23.4.2021	Technical, members of the open work package on self-description	EU	30-40	Matija Cankar, XLAB TOSCA presentation	Presentation
Second SwForum workshop on trustworthy software and open source	29-30.06.2021/ 01.07.2021	Technical: practitioners, RTOs, etc	All Europe (world)		Elisabetta Di Nitto, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Juncal Alonso, Pawel, Nejc, Alfonso de la Fuente	Presentation
SWForum.eu Webinar: Market & Technology Readiness Levels	26.05.2021	Technical: practitioners, RTOs, etc	All Europe (world)	50	Elisabetta Di Nitto, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Juncal Alonso, Nejc, Galia Nedeltcheva	Attendance
Conference Informatics in public administrations/Informatika v javni upravi – IJU 2021	TBD	Public administration, informatics, the decisions makers and their associates, e-service providers/developers	All Europe, attendees mainly from Slovenia	500	SI-MPA team	Presentation
BSides Newcastle 2021	10.09.2021	BSides Newcastle is the weirdest	Worldwide	approx. 500	7bulls team	Presentation

Event	Date	Name & type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Activity
		InfoSec event out there. Last year we went virtual with a 2 day event with speakers from 4 continents. This year we go hybrid offering both the coverage of the virtual events and the opportunity for live events again.				Radość w Piliszek Paweł Skrzypek 7bulls
TOSCA Implementation Stories	27.10.2021	This series of events are suitable for network operators, service providers, cloud brokers, application providers, tooling providers, and so on.	Worldwide	Cca 100	Matija Cankar, Anže Luzar, Nejc Bat – XLAB	Presentation and Demo
H-cloud summit 2021	8.12.2021	Industrial	EU		Leire Orue-Echevarria	Participation in the panel Open Source and standardization
H-cloud summit 2021	8.12.2021	Industrial	EU		Leire Orue-Echevarria	Participation in the final

Event	Date	Name & type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Activity
						SODALIT E event
Sustainability SwForum workshop	19.01.2022	Technical: practitioners, RTOs, etc	All Europe		Elisabetta Di Nitto, Leire Orue-Echevarria, Nejc, Galia Nedeltcheva	Presentation
DevSecOps 2022 https://devsecopsconf.kubedaily.com/index.html#section-about	8.01.2022	DevSecOps Conf is non-profit developer-first platform for sharing and collaborating on open source, cloud native technologies, GitOps, and security domains.	worldwide	+500	7bullsteam	Presentation Radosław Piliszek
The Hack Summit 2021	5.11.2021	Professionals working in the field of broadly defined IT security Management representatives dealing with technical aspects of projects Developers and architects People interested in IT	All Europe	+100	7bullsteam	Presentation Radosław Piliszek

Event	Date	Name & type of audience	Countries addressed	Size of audience	People attending	Activity
		security				
Conf42: DevSecOps 2021	2.12.2021	Conf42 are quality tech conferences , which gather more than 3500 people	All Europe and +	+3000	7bulls team	Presenta tionRado sław Piliszek

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6 Networking activities

PIACERE partners understand the value of collaborating with other projects and initiatives beyond European projects. Some of these are detailed below.

Furthermore, collaboration can come in different flavours. There are technical collaborations, which imply coming together to find a joint solution for a common identified problem, commercial or promotional, more focused on the business side. Collaborations can be just a one-time-thing, or it can be continuous. Finally, collaborations can be with projects, with limited in time joint activities (e.g. Future cloud cluster), or with formal organizations.

6.1 Networking with other European projects

The networking and collaboration with other European projects (see Table 12 below) are a natural process as synergies can be easily found. Unfortunately, due to COVID-19 travelling restrictions concertation events have been virtual. Finding common areas of work with other actions in these circumstances has proven to be more challenging than expected. In spite of that, PIACERE has collaborated with several actions.

Table 12. Networking initiatives with other European projects

No	Project Name	Description of activity
1.	GAIA-X	March 2021: some dissemination actions with GAIA-X WGs. GAIA-X is very interested in the approach of continuous monitoring of infrastructural elements, catalogue rather than cloud services.
2.	SWForum	CSA. Participation in the three workshops, questionnaires, and so on.
3.	H-Cloud	CSA. Participation in the H-Cloud Communication task force: attendance to the monthly meetings.
4.	Future cloud cluster	CSA. Contribution in the position paper and cloud federation reference architecture paper.
5.	Medina	Security tools
6.	SODALITE	IaC management/deployment (not explored yet)
7.	Hub 4Cloud	Participation in the Hub 4Cloud Communication task force: attendance to the monthly meetings. Participation in the 2020, 2021 and 2022 Cloud Summits organized by the CSA.
8.	Future Cloud Cluster	Contribution in the position paper and cloud federation reference architecture paper

H-Cloud is a Coordination and Support action (CSA) that aims at creating a European Cloud Community. Among its tasks it aims at creating a research roadmap on cloud computing, and it

organizes events to create said community. H-Cloud’s successor is **HUB4CLOUD** and has similar objectives to the ones by H-Cloud but the target topics vary.

For the contributions towards the research roadmap, PIACERE has participated in the workshops under invitation to discuss the H-Cloud green and white paper, providing its inputs in an interactive manner during the workshop by means of online voting tools.

For the creation of the community, H-cloud and HUB4CLOUD have a monthly communication task force meeting where various partners of PIACERE participate. In addition to that, PIACERE has participated in the following events organized by H-Cloud and HUB4CLOUD:

- **H-cloud summit 2020¹**: This event was held virtually at the end of November 2020 and consisted on several panel discussions and general presentations. The coordinator Leire Orue-Echevarria participated in the panel that discussed the challenges in edge and cloud computing.

Parallel Session: The Cloud-edge continuum: A key building block of EU data spaces; Moderator: Dr Sebastian Robitzsch (InterDigital Europe)

FROM DIGITAL EUROPE TO THE HIGH IMPACT PROJECT - THE ROLE OF CLOUD COMPUTING

🕒 10:40-11:40

👤 46 participants signed up for this session

DESCRIPTION:

This thematic session includes presentations related to the EU key priority "The Cloud-edge continuum: A key building block of EU data spaces".

Speakers:

- Dr Angelo Corsaro - CTO, ADLINK
 - Presentation: Data Decentralisation for Efficiency, Privacy and Fair Monetisation
- Klaas Wierenga - Chief Information & Technology Officer, GÉANT
 - Presentation: Federated identity as an essential building block for EU data spaces
- Dr Leire Orue-Echevarria Arrieta - Cloud Continuum Project Director, Technalia
 - Presentation: Challenges in the deployment and operation of self-healing applications on the cloud-edge continuum
- Dr Harald Schoening - Vice President Research, Software AG
 - Presentation: The data continuum

Moderator: Dr Sebastian Robitzsch - Senior Staff Engineer, InterDigital Europe

Figure 24. H-cloud summit 2020 agenda

- **Digital Autonomy in the Computing Continuum Workshop²**: held virtually on November 11th, 2021. This workshop was organized by the European Commission with the collaboration of the CSAs H-Cloud, HUB4Clout, NGIOT and SWForum. The participation of Leire Orue-Echevarria consisted on a discussion in a panel.

¹ <https://h-cloud-summit.b2match.io/>

² https://www.h-cloud.eu/event/ec-virtual-event-digital-autonomy-in-the-computing-continuum/?instance_id=119

Figure 25. Digital Autonomy in the Computing Continuum Workshop

- **H-cloud summit 2021³**: PIACERE participated with Leire Orue-Echevarria as a speaker at the panel “Cloud Standardization and Open-Source for a Robust Digital Cloud Landscape”, which was held virtually on December 8th, 2021 in a collocated session of the CloudExpo Europe. The collaboration involved the participation in a panel.

Figure 26. H-cloud summit 2021

- **Horizon Cloud summit 2022⁴**: PIACERE participated with Juncal Alonso as a speaker at the panel “Trends and roadmap in the computing continuum research”, which was held on May 12th, 2022 in a collocated session of the CloudExpo Europe in Frankfurt. She provided the talk :”DevOps, IaC and AI: The golden triplet”, through which she introduced

³ <https://www.h-cloud.eu/event/horizon-cloud-summit-2021/>

⁴ <https://www.h-cloud.eu/event/horizon-cloud-summit-2021/>

Figure 27. PIACERE presentation in Cloud Summit 2022

Figure 28. Horizon Cloud Summit 2022

PIACERE was invited to participate in the **SODALITE** Final event. SODALITE is a European project focused on Infrastructure as Code and deals with several issues that PIACERE also aims to resolve. Two partners of that project participate in PIACERE, namely Politecnico di Milano and XLAB. The approach of both projects differs but the philosophy is rather similar and some of the results of SODALITE may be extended in PIACERE. In this event, the project coordinator of PIACERE presented the similarities of the projects, the differences, and the ways in which the results of SODALITE will be adopted.

The poster for the Sodalite Final Event features a blue and white color scheme with a background of glowing blue nodes and lines. At the top left is the Sodalite logo, a blue square with a white geometric pattern. To its right, the text 'Sodalite' is written in a large, bold, sans-serif font. Further right, 'Final Event' is written in a smaller, bold, sans-serif font. Below this, the event's theme is stated: 'Increasing design and runtime effectiveness of software-defined infrastructures over dynamic heterogeneous execution environments'. To the right of the theme, the event details are listed: 'Project results, use cases, and best practices', 'Thursday, December 9th, 2021', '11:30 - 14:00', and 'Virtual Workshop'. The main body of the poster lists several topics and speakers, including 'Welcome and Introduction to SODALITE' by Nejc Bat, 'Layer-based business models for HPC and Multicloud optimisation' by Joao Costa, a 'Demo: Specification and Deployment of Snow Water use case using SODALITE' by Giovanni Quattrocchi and Rocío Nahime, and 'SODALITE Use Cases' which includes 'KnowGo Car data management and services platform for connected vehicles' by Paul Mundt, 'In silico spinal trials for bone operations assessment and decision-support system' by Ralf Schneider, and 'Water availability prediction from public mountain images' by Piero Fraternali. A panel titled 'Collaboration and synergies with H2020 Projects' is moderated by Kalman Meth, IBM, and includes three bullet points about RADON, PIACERE, and LEXIS projects. At the bottom, logos for Horizon Cloud, Summit 2021, Cloud Expo Europe, RADON, PIACERE, and LEXIS are displayed. A small text at the bottom right states: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 625480'.

Figure 29. SODALITE Final event

SWForum is another Coordination and Support Action (CSA), but this one in the field of Software Technologies, cybersecurity and digital infrastructures. SWForum has organized three events in which representatives of PIACERE have been present:

- **First SWForum workshop**⁵: this workshop was organized as a call for papers workshop with keynotes and discussions. It was a three-day long event where PIACERE presented a paper, that was accepted. The paper appears in the CEUR proceedings and are open access.
- **Second SWForum workshop**⁶: the second workshop was also a three-day long workshop under the title “Research Challenges, Collaboration, and Coordination in European Software Engineering Projects”. Each day was devoted to one of the topics above,

⁵ <https://swforum.eu/events/first-swforumeu-workshop-trustworthy-software-and-open-source>

⁶ <https://swforum.eu/events/second-swforumeu-workshop>

namely 1) to discuss about open research challenges that are of interest in the European Software Engineering community; 2) to discuss about collaboration opportunities among European projects in the area of software engineering; and 3) to understand how to develop a self-sustaining and self-governed research forum at the European level. PIACERE presented a research challenge based on the current challenges found on the project and participated actively in the discussions held all three days.

- **SWForum Governance model workshop:** this workshop was organized with the aim of identifying whether the creation of a new software engineering community is needed or any other alternative may be more suitable, such as the creation of a federation of existing communities or the expansion of national ones. The participation in this workshop was under invitation. Coordinators and participants of European projects participated along with the European Commission and other relevant experts of the software community. PIACERE participated in the discussions in an active manner need of creating a software engineering community and how policymakers can be influenced to keep the funding on the topics of software engineering.

Moreover, PIACERE appears in the **project hub** that SWForum has created and has participated in the **MTRL assessment**.

Figure 30. PIACERE in the Project Hub of SWForum

Figure 31. PIACERE details in the SWForum project Hub

6.2 Networking with the Future Cloud Cluster

The Future Cloud Cluster was created by the European Commission with the aim of “*providing a forum for discussion and collaboration for research and innovation initiatives that address next generation Cloud Computing challenges and issues, including diverse forms of distributed computing (Cloud, Multi-Cloud, Edge, Fog, Ad-hoc and Mobile computing)*”⁷.

During this period, the work of the cluster has revolved around two main topics:

- **Research roadmaps**⁸: the research roadmap released in 2020 is a revision of the research areas described in 2018 and cover the areas of Edge computing, Multi-Cloud, Computing continuum and Federated Cloud. It aimed at providing input from on-going and past project participants to the European Commission for the definition of new work programmes in the context of Horizon Europe. Thirteen research areas were identified and discussed. PIACERE participated in drafting several of these areas or contributing thereof. The final paper can be found online.
- **Cloud Federation Reference Architecture**⁹: at the request of the European Commission, several projects and members of the Future Cloud cluster contributed in the definition of a reference architecture of a European cloud federation. PIACERE participated in the discussions held and contributed to the document in various sections. Furthermore, PIACERE was also mapped as one of the research projects that have provided or will provide research findings in that can contribute to the realisation of the reference architecture building blocks. The final paper can be found online.

⁷ <https://eucloudclusters.wordpress.com/future-cloud/>

⁸ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Qw-PIR5D4H-ZZ4-CZ1pXRkf8IUzjLMzE/view?usp=sharing>

⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Kw6j41bcGw8v_o8KW18TkE0xe4kxBMIR/view?usp=sharing

Figure 32. Mapping of Research projects to Reference Architecture layers. PIACERE is featured among the selected projects.

6.3 Networking with Gaia-x

Gaia-X¹⁰ is an initiative initially launched by Germany and France but now European that aims at creating a European federated data infrastructure.

Several partners of PIACERE are members of the Gaia-X AISBL association and participate actively in the working groups of Gaia-X since at least June 2020. Some of the most relevant activities related to PIACERE include:

- Participation in the working group of **Compliance** (not active any more at the time of writing this deliverable in March 2022), where PIACERE was presented in November 2019, even before the project started. Activity carried out by TECNALIA.
- Participation in the working group **Self-Description**, where the attributes defined in the PIACERE IEC (Infrastructural Elements Catalogue) were shared to be considered as baseline for the discussion. The group of Self-Description has defined the mandatory attributes of how to describe a cloud service provider but not how to describe a service or resource. Since that activity was already done in the IEC for VM, storage and database, the knowledge was shared with the group. This is still under discussion. Activity carried out by TECNALIA.
- Development of the **orchestrator**, one of the Lots awarded in the German project **GXFS**¹¹, which is tightly related to the IEM being developed in PIACERE. While the GXFS is based on TOSCA, it includes some APIs to be able to deploy software using Ansible and Terraform, the two languages supported by the IEM. Work is being carried out to understand how to integrate both views and contribute, with the IEM, to Gaia-X Open Source Software repository. Activity carried out by XLAB (company awarded the contract) and TECNALIA (responsible of the IEM).
- **Online meeting** with Pierre Gronlier, CTO of Gaia-X in spring 2021, where PIACERE was presented, among other projects and solutions that TECNALIA has been working on for the past years.

The **Gaia-X Spanish Hub Working Group on Industry 4.0** was launched on February 15th, 2022 in Bilbao. The event was organized by the Secretary of State of Digitalization and Artificial Intelligence (SEDIA), the Office for Data (“Oficina del dato”) of the Spanish Government and the

¹⁰ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

¹¹ <https://www.gxfs.eu/>

Department of Economic Development of the Basque Government. The workshop had in its agenda the speeches of the Spanish Secretary of State Carme Artigas and the Vice minister of technology, innovation and digital transformation of the Basque Country, Estibaliz Hernaez. TECNALIA was also among the presenters, being a co-lead of the working group. The presentation revolved around the challenges of a cloud federation and data spaces in the industry and as part of a good practice for the cloud federation part, PIACERE was briefly introduced and presented to the audience. The event was hybrid and recorded.

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7 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the dissemination, communication and networking activities carried out as part of the PIACERE project in the first reporting period (18 months) of the project lifetime.

The achievement of the majority of the defined KPIs for the current period demonstrates that the strategy followed is appropriate. Comparing the expected results with the achieved ones, we acknowledge that there is no need to change the dissemination and communication plans for the time being.

The next publication of these activities will be in deliverable D8.6, where the final outcome will be reported.

Although this deliverable covers the main activities that partners undertook to disseminate and communicate the results of the project, they will be continuously updated along the project timeframe. This includes also website, blog entries, deliverables, brochures, videos, and source code. Also, as mentioned beforehand, the different documents will also have several interactions, with different focus, goal and target audience.

DRAFT

8 References

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Appendix A: PIACERE Press Release in different languages

The following figures show the content of the press releases translated into the different languages of the partners, specifically Italian, Polish, Slovenian, and Spanish.

Press Release

PIACERE: A DevSecOps framework for secure IaC Development and Operation.

Milano, Italy, April 2022

PIACERE è un progetto di ricerca H2020 finanziato dalla Commissione Europea in un periodo di tre anni. L'obiettivo principale di PIACERE è la programmazione di infrastrutture affidabili mediante *Infrastructure-as-Code (IaC)* in un framework sicuro.

Il consorzio PIACERE, guidato da TECNALIA, riunisce un insieme equilibrato di partner accademici e industriali, che svolgono ruoli chiave nell'ecosistema SecDevOps dell'UE: ERICSSON, PRODEVELOP, POLIMI, HPE, XLAB, GOV.S, 7BULLS.COM e TECNALIA provengono da quattro diversi paesi, che rappresentano l'Europa settentrionale e meridionale. A TECNALIA è affidata la guida del consorzio.

PIACERE mira ad aumentare la produttività dei team DevOps nello sviluppo e nel funzionamento di IaC attraverso il provisioning di un framework DevSecOps integrato. I team DevOps possono programmare IaC come se stessero programmando qualsiasi applicazione software.

PIACERE supporterà le diverse attività DevSecOps attraverso un unico ambiente integrato per lo sviluppo (IDE) di codice infrastrutturale che unificerà l'automazione delle principali attività DevSecOps e ridurrà la curva di apprendimento per i nuovi team DevSecOps. PIACERE consentirà ai team DevSecOps di modellare diversi ambienti infrastrutturali, per mezzo di astrazioni, attraverso un nuovo DevOps Modeling Language (DOML), nascondendo così le specificità e gli aspetti tecnici delle soluzioni attuali e aumentando la produttività di questi team. Inoltre, PIACERE fornirà anche un generatore di codice infrastrutturale estensibile (ICG), che traduce DOML in file sorgente per diversi strumenti IaC esistenti, per ridurre il tempo necessario per la creazione di codice infrastrutturale per applicazioni complesse. I meccanismi di estensibilità previsti (DOML-E) garantiranno la sostenibilità e la longevità dell'approccio PIACERE e della suite di strumenti (nuovi linguaggi e protocolli che possono apparire nel prossimo futuro).

Un'altra innovazione chiave di PIACERE è un toolkit completo per la verifica e l'affidabilità. In primo luogo, uno strumento di verifica (VT), che applicherà l'analisi statica sia al modello astratto che al relativo codice infrastrutturale, per eseguire controlli di coerenza e altre verifiche di qualità secondo le migliori pratiche identificate. In secondo luogo, un IaC Code Security Inspector che offrirà una forma di Static Analysis Security Testing (SAST) controllando il codice IaC rispetto ai problemi noti di sicurezza informatica (configurazioni errate, uso di librerie non sicure, modelli di configurazione non sicuri). In terzo luogo, un Component Security Inspector che, analizzando anche il codice IaC, segnala le potenziali vulnerabilità e propone potenziali fix. Quarto, un ambiente "Canary" che consentirà di testare in modo unitario il comportamento del codice infrastrutturale in un ambiente isolato, consentendo la simulazione delle condizioni per l'ambiente di produzione e identificando alcuni degli anti-pattern più comuni.

Nella parte Ops del ciclo di vita DevSecOps, PIACERE presenta anche diverse innovazioni chiave: La piattaforma ottimizzata (IOP) presenterà ai team DevSecOps le configurazioni di distribuzione più appropriate che soddisfano al meglio i vincoli definiti al di fuori del loro catalogo di servizi, risorse ed elementi infrastrutturali mediante algoritmi di ottimizzazione. La piattaforma di esecuzione pianificherà, preparerà e fornirà automaticamente l'infrastruttura e pianificherà, preparerà e installerà gli elementi software corrispondenti necessari per il corretto funzionamento dell'applicazione. A

runtime, PIACERE monitorerà continuamente le metriche associate agli NFR misurabili definiti (es. performance, disponibilità e sicurezza attraverso il monitoraggio della sicurezza in runtime) e sarà in grado di autoapprendere, implementando algoritmi di machine learning e realizzando una strategia di apprendimento incrementale analizzando continuamente le divergenze nei confini delle decisioni e rilevando le anomalie nelle metriche raccolte, conservando solo i dati più aggiornati per evitare il degrado del modello. Ogni volta che questi meccanismi di autoapprendimento rilevano un'anomalia o una potenziale violazione dello SLA, verrà attivato un allarme e verrà avviato un meccanismo di auto-riparazione. Il meccanismo di auto-riparazione comporterà il riavvio di un algoritmo di ottimizzazione per il dominio del problema effettivo e una piattaforma di esecuzione automatica, monitoraggio e così via.

L'approccio e il set di strumenti PIACERE saranno valutati in tre casi d'uso reali. SI-MPA implementerà uno scenario per il Ministero della Pubblica Amministrazione sloveno, Prodevelop lo convaliderà nella gestione delle infrastrutture marittime critiche ed Ericsson verificherà la soluzione in un caso d'uso di pubblica sicurezza su IoT in 5G.

PIACERE realizzerà inoltre i seguenti benefici attesi:

- Rendere la creazione del codice infrastrutturale più accessibile ai team DevSecOps
- Aumentare la qualità, la sicurezza, l'affidabilità e l'evolubilità del codice infrastrutturale
- Garantire la continuità aziendale fornendo meccanismi di auto-riparazione, anticipando i guasti e le violazioni
- Consentire all'IaC di apprendere da sé dalle condizioni precedenti che hanno innescato situazioni impreviste

In questo primo anno di progetto, il lavoro si è concentrato sulla definizione dell'architettura generale di PIACERE, nonché sullo sviluppo della prima versione del framework integrato che sarà validata dagli use case.

Ultime notizie e informazioni disponibili su: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

Questo progetto ha ricevuto finanziamenti dal programma di ricerca e innovazione Horizon 2020 dell'Unione Europea sull'accordo di

sovvenzione n. 101000162

Contatto

Galina Nedelcheva, POLIMI
galina.nedelcheva@polimi.it
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32
20133 Milano

Figure 33. PIACERE Press Release in Italian

Informacja Prasowa

PIACERE: Framework DevSecOps dla bezpiecznego rozwoju i obsługi IaC

Warszawa, Kwiecień 2022

PIACERE to trzyletni projekt badawczy finansowany przez Komisję Europejską w ramach programu Horyzont 2020. Głównym celem projektu jest programowanie zaufanych skodyfikowanych infrastruktur w bezpiecznym frameworku.

Konsorcjum PIACERE stanowi zrównoważony zespół partnerów akademickich i przemysłowych, grających kluczową rolę w unijnym ekosystemie DevSecOps. Są to ERICSSON, PRODEVELOP, POLIMI, HPE, XLAB, GOV.SI, SŁOWEŃSKIE MINISTERSTWO ADMINISTRACJI PUBLICZNEJ (SI-MPA), 7BULLS.COM i TECNALIA, - reprezentanci czterech różnych krajów Północnej i Południowej Europy. Misja kierowania działaniami konsorcjum została powierzona firmie TECNALIA.

PIACERE ma na celu zwiększenie produktywności zespołów DevOps w obszarze rozwoju i obsługi IaC poprzez dostarczenie zintegrowanego frameworku DevSecOps. Zespoły DevOps mogą programować IaC tak, jak gdyby programowały jakikolwiek inną aplikację.

PIACERE ma wspierać wykonywanie czynności w zakresie DevSecOps za pośrednictwem jednego, zintegrowanego środowiska programistycznego (IDE), dzięki któremu tworzony jest kod infrastrukturalny, ujednoliciwszy automatyzację głównych działań DevSecOps i skracający krzywą uczenia się nowych zespołów DevSecOps. PIACERE umożliwił zespołom DevSecOps modelowanie wielorakich środowisk infrastruktury dzięki abstrakcjom, poprzez innowacyjny język **DevOps Modeling Language (DOML)**, ukrywając tym samym specyfikę i techniczne aspekty obecnych rozwiązań i zwiększając produktywność zespołów specjalistów. Co więcej, wraz z PIACERE zapewniony zostanie dostęp do modułowego generatora kodów, **Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG)**, tłumaczącego DOML na pliki źródłowe dla różnych istniejących narzędzi, w celu redukcji czasu potrzebnego do stworzenia kodu infrastrukturalnego do zaawansowanych aplikacji. Dostarczone **extensibility mechanisms (DOML-E)** zapewnią zrównoważenie i ponadczasowość PIACERE oraz towarzyszącego mu pakietu narzędzi (biorąc pod uwagę nowe języki i protokoły, jakie mogą pojawić się w bliższej przyszłości).

Kolejnym kluczowym i innowacyjnym elementem PIACERE jest kompleksowy zestaw narzędzi służący do weryfikacji i sprawdzania wiarygodności. Po pierwsze, **verification tool (VT)**, które dzięki zastosowaniu analizy statystycznej, zarówno do modelu abstrakcyjnego, jak i do powiązanego kodu infrastrukturalnego, może dokonywać kontroli spójności oraz weryfikować inne wskaźniki jakości w odniesieniu do ustalonych dobrych praktyk. Po drugie, **IaC Code Security Inspector** - narzędzie oferujące formę testów bezpieczeństwa analizy statycznej (SAST), sprawdzając kod IaC pod kątem znanych, pojawiających się problemów z cyberbezpieczeństwem (błędne konfiguracje, korzystanie z niebezpiecznych bibliotek, wzorce niebezpiecznych konfiguracji). Po trzecie, **Component Security Inspector**, który dzięki analizie kodu IaC, raportuje potencjalne luki w zabezpieczeniach i proponuje

sposoby na ich eliminację. Po czwarte, **Canary environment** - narzędzie pozwalające na przeprowadzanie testów jednostkowych zachowania kodu infrastrukturalnego w izolowanym środowisku, co umożliwi symulację warunków środowiska produkcyjnego i rozpoznanie niektórych z najczęściej pojawiających się antywzorów.

W części operacyjnej (Ops) cyklu życia DevSecOps PIACERE również prezentuje kilka istotnych innowacji. **Optimized Platform (OP)**, czyli platforma optymalizująca, zaprezentuje zespołom DevSecOps najbardziej odpowiednią konfigurację wdrożenia, która za sprawą algorytmów optymalizacji będzie w jak największym stopniu pokrywać się ze zdefiniowanymi przez zespół ograniczeniami dotyczącymi usług, zasobów i elementów infrastruktury. **Execution Platform**, czyli platforma wykonawcza, będzie zarówno automatycznie planować, przygotowywać i wdrażać infrastrukturę, jak i zadba o instalację odpowiednich elementów oprogramowania koniecznych do bezproblemowego działania aplikacji. W czasie pracy PIACERE będzie stale **monitorować metryki** związane z mierzalnymi wymaganiami niefunkcjonalnymi NFR (wydajność, dostępność, bezpieczeństwo itp.). Pomiar bezpieczeństwa będzie odbywał się dzięki komponentowi **runtime security monitoring**. PIACERE będzie frameworkiem zdolnym do **samouczenia**, implementując algorytmy uczenia maszynowego oraz realizując strategię uczenia przystosowanego poprzez ciągłą analizę rozbieżności w granicach decyzji i wykrywanie anomalii w zbieranych metrykach, zachowując tylko najbardziej aktualne dane celem uniknięcia degradacji modelu. Za każdym razem, gdy **mechanizmy samouczenia** wykryją anomalie lub potencjalne naruszenie umowy o gwarantowanym poziomie świadczenia usług (SLA), wywołany zostanie alarm, a **mechanizmy samonaprawcze** będą uruchamiane. Taka sytuacja będzie wiązała się z ponownym uruchomieniem algorytmu optymalizacji w domenie problemu oraz automatyczne uruchomienie platformy wykonawczej, systemu monitorowania itd.

Podjęcie PIACERE i testów towarzyszących mu narzędzi zostaną ocenione w trzech rzeczywistych przypadkach użycia: SI-MPA wdroży scenariusz dla Słoweńskiego Ministerstwa Administracji Publicznej, PRODEVELOP weryfikuje projekt na przykładzie Zarządzenia Krytyczną Infrastrukturą Nadmorską, zaś Ericsson sprawdzi propozycje rozwiązania na przykładzie **Bezpieczeństwa Publicznego w IoT w 5G**.

PIACERE przyniesie również inne korzyści:

- ułatwienie procesu tworzenia kodu infrastrukturalnego dla zespołów DevSecOps,
- podniesienie poziomu jakości, bezpieczeństwa, solidności i ewoluwalności kodu infrastrukturalnego,
- zapewnienie ciągłości działania firm poprzez zastosowanie mechanizmów samonaprawczych w momencie przewidywania naruszeń i awarii,
- umożliwienie IaC samouczenia się na podstawie wcześniejszych warunków, które odpowiadały za wystąpienie nieprzewidywanych sytuacji.

W pierwszym roku prac nad projektem skupiono się na zdefiniowaniu architektury ogólnej PIACERE, a także na rozwinięciu pierwszej wersji zintegrowanej struktury, która zostanie zweryfikowana w kolejnych latach trwania projektu na podstawie przypadków wdrożenia.

Aktualizacje i inne informacje dotyczące projektu dostępne są na stronie: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

Projekt otrzymał dofinansowanie w ramach unijnego programu badań i innowacji "Horyzont 2020", w ramach grantu nr 101000162.

Kontakt:
Elżbieta Kalbarczyk, PR specjalistka
ekalbarczyk@7bulls.com
7bulls.com Sp. z o.o.
al. Sucho 8
00-582 Warszawa

Figure 34. PIACERE Press Release in Polish

Sporočilo za javnost

PIACERE: DevSecOps okvir za varen razvoj in delovanje infrastrukture kot kode (IaC)

PIACERE je triletni raziskovalni projekt financiran s strani Evropske Komisije v okviru evropskega programa za raziskave in inovacije Obzorje 2020. Glavni cilj projekta je programiranje zanesljive infrastrukture kot kode v varnem okviru.

Konzorcij PIACERE pod vodstvom TECNALIA sestavlja uravnotežen nabor akademskih in industrijskih partnerjev, ki igrajo ključno vlogo v evropskem DevSecOps ekosistemu - ERICSSON, PRODEVOP, POLIMI, HPE, XLAB, GUV.SI, 7BULLS.COM in TECNALIA, ki prihajajo iz štirih različnih držav in zastopajo severno in južno Evropo. Vodenje konzorcija pa je bilo zaupano družbi TECNALIA.

Cilj projekta PIACERE je povežati produktivnost DevOps ekip pri razvoju in delovanju infrastrukture kot kode (IaC) z zagotavljanjem integriranega DevSecOps okvira. DevOps ekipe lahko programirajo infrastrukturo kot kode (IaC), kot bi programirale katere koli programske aplikacije.

PIACERE bo podpiral različne DevSecOps dejavnosti z uporabo enotnega integriranega okolja za razvoj infrastrukturne kode (IDE), ki bo pomenila avtomatizacijo glavnih DevSecOps dejavnosti in skrājala krivuljo učenja za nove DevSecOps ekipe. PIACERE bo DevSecOps ekipam omogočil modeliranje različnih infrastrukturnih okolij s pomočjo abstrakcij v novem DevOps jeziku za modeliranje (DOML), s tem pa skrājal posebnosti in tehnične značilnosti trenutnih rešitev ter povečal produktivnost teh ekip. Poleg tega bo PIACERE zagotovil tudi razširjen generator infrastrukturne kode (ICG), ki bo prevedel DOML v izvorne datoteke za različna obstoječa orodja IaC in tako skrājajl čas, potreben za ustvarjanje infrastrukturne kode za kompleksne aplikacije. Zagotovljeni mehanizmi razširjenosti (DOML-E) bodo omogočili trajnost in dolgotrajnost pristopa in nabora orodij PIACERE (novi jeziki in protokoli, ki se lahko pojavijo v bližnji prihodnosti).

Druge ključne inovacije projekta PIACERE je celovit nabor orodij za preverjanje in zanesljivost. Prvič, orodje za preverjanje (VT), ki bo uporabljalo statistično analizo tako za abstraktni model kot za povezano infrastrukturo koda, za izvajanje preverjanja skladnosti in drugih preverjanj kakovosti v skladu z opredeljenimi najboljšimi praksami. Drugič, varnostni inšpektor kode IaC, ki bo ponujal obliko varnostnega testiranja s statistično analizo (SAST) s preverjanjem kode IaC glede na zoznane težave kibernetске varnosti (napačne konfiguracije, uporaba nezaščitenih knjižnic, nezaščiteni konfiguracijski vzorci). Tretjič, inšpektor za varnost komponent, ki z analizo kode IaC poroča o morebitnih ranljivostih in predlaga morebitne popravke. Četrto, okolje Canary, ki bo omogočilo testiranje enote obnašanja infrastrukturne kode v izoliranem okolju, kar bi omogočilo simulacijo pogojev za produkcijsko okolje in prepoznalo nekatere najpogostejše provizore.

Tudi v operativnem delu DevSecOps življenjskega cikle PIACERE predstavlja več ključnih inovacij: Optimizirana platforma (IOP) bo DevSecOps ekipam s pomočjo optimizacijskih algoritmov iz kataloga storitev, vrov in infrastrukturnih elementov predstavila neustreznejše konfiguracije za namestitve glede na opredeljene omejitve. Izvedbena platforma bo samodejno načrtovala, pripravila in zagotovila infrastrukturo ter načrtovala, pripravila in namestila ustrezne elemente programske

opreme, potrebne za nemoteno delovanje aplikacije. Med izvajanjem bo PIACERE stalno spremljal metrike, povezane z opredeljenimi merljivimi NFR (npr. zmožljivost, razpoložljivost in varnost s spremljanjem varnosti med izvajanjem), in se bo sposoben samodejno z izvajanjem algoritmov strojnega učenja in ureševanjem strategij postopnega učenja z nenehnim analiziranjem odstopanj na mejah odločanja in odkrivanjem anomalij v zbranih metrikih, pri čemer bo hranil le najnovejše podatke, da bi s tem preprečil degradacijo modela. Kadar ti mehanizmi samoučenja zaznajo nepravilnost ali morebitno kršitev, se sprožita alarm in mehanizem samozdravljenja. Slednji bo vključeval ponovni zagon optimizacijskega algoritma za dejansko problemsko področje in platformo za samodejno izvajanje, spremljanje, itd.

Pristop in nabor orodij PIACERE bosta ocenjena v treh praktičnih primerih uporabe. SI-MPA bo izvedla scenarij za Ministrstvo za javno upravo Republike Slovenije. Predevlop ga bo potrdil v primeru upravljanja kritične pomorske infrastrukture, Ericsson pa bo rešitev preveril v primeru uporabe javne varnosti na internetu stvari (IoT) v 5G.

PIACERE bo prinesel tudi naslednje pričakovane koristi:

- Narediti ustvarjanje takšne infrastrukturne kode bolj dostopno DevSecOps ekipam.
- Povečanje kakovosti, varnosti, zanesljivosti in možnosti razvoja infrastrukturne kode.
- Zagotavljanje neprekinjenega poslovanja z zagotavljanjem mehanizmov samozdravljenja, ki preprečujevajo napake in kršitve.
- Omogočanje samoučenja sistema IaC na podlagi prejšnjih pogojev, ki so sprožili nepričakovane situacije.

V prvem letu projekta je bilo delo osredotočeno na opredelitev splošne arhitekture PIACERE ter na razvoj prve različice integriranega okvira, ki bo potrjen s primeri uporabe.

Več informacij o projektu: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

Projekt PIACERE je prejel sredstva iz programa Evropske unije za raziskave in inovacije Obzorje 2020 na podlagi o dodeliti nepovratnih sredstev št. 101000162

Kontakt

Lujša Korber
lujsha.korber@xlab.si
 XLAB d.o.o., Pot za Brdno 100, SI-1000 Ljubljana
 Slovenija, EU
 Tel.: +386 1244 77 50

Figure 35. PIACERE Press Release in Slovenian

Press Release

PIACERE: un marco DevSecOps para el desarrollo y la operación seguros de IaC.

Bilbao, Spain, April 2022

PIACERE es un proyecto de investigación H2020 financiado por la Comisión Europea durante un periodo de tres años. El principal objetivo de PIACERE es programar una infraestructura confiable As Code en un marco seguro.

El consorcio PIACERE, liderado por TECNALIA, reúne un conjunto equilibrado de socios académicos e industriales, que desempeñan un papel clave en el ecosistema DevSecOps de la UE. ERICSSON, PRODEVOP, POLIMI, HPE, XLAB, GUV.SI, 7BULLS.COM y TECNALIA, pertenecen a cuatro países diferentes, que representan el norte y el sur de Europa. Se ha entendido a TECNALIA el liderazgo del consorcio.

PIACERE tiene como objetivo aumentar la productividad de los equipos DevOps en el desarrollo y operación de IaC a través del aprovisionamiento de un marco integrado DevSecOps. Los equipos de DevOps pueden programar IaC como si estuvieran programando cualquier aplicación de software.

PIACERE respaldará las diferentes actividades de DevSecOps a través de un único entorno integrado para desarrollar (IDE) código de infraestructura que unificará la automatización de las principales actividades de DevSecOps y acortará la curva de aprendizaje para los nuevos equipos de DevSecOps. PIACERE permitirá a los equipos DevSecOps modular diferentes entornos de infraestructura, por medio de abstracciones, a través de un novedoso lenguaje de Modelado DevOps (DOML), ocultando así las especificidades y tecnicismos de las soluciones actuales y aumentando la productividad de estos equipos. Además, PIACERE también proporcionará un generador de código de infraestructura extensible (ICG), que traduce DOML en archivos fuente para diferentes herramientas IaC existentes, para reducir el tiempo necesario para crear código de infraestructura para aplicaciones complejas. Los mecanismos de extensibilidad proporcionados (DOML-E) garantizarán la sostenibilidad y la longevidad del enfoque y el conjunto de herramientas de PIACERE [nuevos lenguajes y protocolos que pueden aparecer en un futuro próximo].

Otra innovación clave de PIACERE es un completo conjunto de herramientas para la verificación y la confiabilidad. En primer lugar, una herramienta de verificación (VT), que aplicará análisis estático tanto al modelo abstracto como al código de infraestructura relacionado, para ejecutar controles de consistencia y otras verificaciones de calidad de acuerdo con las mejores prácticas identificadas. En segundo lugar, un inspector de seguridad del código de IaC que ofrecerá una forma de prueba de seguridad de análisis estático (SAST) comparando el código de IaC con los problemas de ciberseguridad conocidos (configuraciones incorrectas, uso de bibliotecas no seguras, patrones de configuración no seguros). En tercer lugar, un inspector de seguridad de componentes que, al analizar también el código IaC, informa sobre las posibles vulnerabilidades y propone posibles soluciones. En cuarto lugar, un entorno Canary que permitirá realizar pruebas unitarias del comportamiento del código de infraestructura en un entorno aislado, lo que permitirá simular las condiciones del entorno de producción e identificar algunos de los antipatrones más habituales.

En la parte de operaciones del ciclo de vida de DevSecOps, PIACERE también presenta varias innovaciones clave: La plataforma optimizada (IOP) presentará a los equipos de DevSecOps las configuraciones de implementación más apropiadas que mejor cumplan con las restricciones

definidas de su catálogo de servicios, recursos y elementos de infraestructura, mediante algoritmos de optimización. La plataforma de ejecución planificará, preparará y aprovisionará automáticamente la infraestructura y planificará, preparará e instalará los elementos de software correspondientes necesarios para que la aplicación se ejecute sin problemas. En tiempo de ejecución, PIACERE monitorizará continuamente las métricas asociadas con los NFR medibles definidos (por ejemplo, rendimiento, disponibilidad y seguridad) a través de la monitorización de seguridad en tiempo de ejecución y podrá aprender por sí mismo, implementar algoritmos de aprendizaje automático y realizar una estrategia de aprendizaje incremental, analizando continuamente las divergencias en los límites de decisión y detectando anomalías en las métricas que se recopilan, conservando solo los datos más actualizados para evitar la degradación del modelo. Siempre que estos mecanismos de autoaprendizaje detecten una anomalía o una posible violación de SLA, se activará una alarma y se iniciará un mecanismo de autorreparación. Un mecanismo de autorreparación implicará lanzar nuevamente un algoritmo de optimización para el dominio del problema real y una plataforma de ejecución automática, monitorización, etc.

El enfoque y el conjunto de herramientas de PIACERE se evaluarán en tres casos de uso reales. SI-MPA implementará un escenario para el Ministerio de Administraciones Públicas de España, Prodevlop lo validará en Gestión de Infraestructuras marítimas críticas y Ericsson verificará la solución en un caso de uso de Seguridad pública en IoT en 5G.

Los beneficios que se esperan de PIACERE serán:

- Hacer que la creación de dicho código de infraestructura sea más accesible para los equipos de DevSecOps
- Aumentar la calidad, la seguridad, la confiabilidad y la capacidad de evolución del código de infraestructura
- Garantizar la continuidad del negocio al proporcionar mecanismos de autocuración, anticipación de fallos y violaciones.
- Permitir que IaC aprenda por sí mismo de las condiciones previas que desencadenaron situaciones inesperadas

En este primer año del proyecto, el trabajo se ha centrado en la definición de la arquitectura general de PIACERE, así como en el desarrollo de la primera versión del framework integrado que será validado por los casos de uso.

Últimas noticias e información disponible en: <https://www.piacere-project.eu/>

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del programa de Investigación e Innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea en el marco de subvención No 101000162

Miliana Jorda, Dissemination and Communication Manager in PIACERE. TECNALIA
 miliana.jorda@tecnalia.com
 Parque Científico y Tecnológico de Bilbao, C/Getxo, Edificio 700. E-48160 Derio (Bizkaia)
 Tel.: +34 940 500 000 (internacional) (calle: 1-34) 946 480 850

Figure 36. PIACERE Press Release in Spanish